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Escola Superior d'Enginyeries Industrial,
Aeroespacial i Audiovisual de Terrassa

Design of a low-cost high voltage rectifier for experiments with DC arcs

Document:

Annex

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Degree:

Bachelor in Electrical Engineering

Bachelor in Industrial Electronics and Automatic Control Engineering

Examination session:

Winter 2024

BACHELOR FINAL THESIS

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Note: All material here displayed can be found on <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10476892>.

Appendix A

Distribution Transformer

Characterization: *MATLAB* Code

```

1 %% Open Circuit Tests
2 clear all
3 V0ph=[49.72 48.58 50.05]; %V
4 %Dy config
5 I0=[1.051 0.950 1.002];%A
6 degreeOffsetVoid=[54.9498 58.7950 68.0847];%deg
7 TR=[34.916/1053 34.467/875 35.16/1122];%V/V
8 %
9 for i=1:3
10 P0ph(i)=V0ph(i)*I0(i)*cosd(degreeOffsetVoid(i));
11 Rc(i)=(V0ph(i)^2)/P0ph(i);
12 Xm(i)=(V0ph(i))^2/(sqrt((V0ph(i)*I0(i))^2-P0ph(i)^2));
13 end
14 %% SC Tests
15 Uscphase=[5.2643 5.3214 5.4460]/sqrt(3); %V
16 Isc=[11.780 5.209 6.689]; %A
17 degreeOffsetSC=49.95;%deg
18 %
19 for i=1:3
20 ISCvect(i)=Isc(i)*(cosd(degreeOffsetSC)+1i*sind(-degreeOffsetSC));
21 Zcc(i)=Uscphase(i)/ISCvect(i);
22 end
23 Req=real(Zcc);
24 Xeq=imag(Zcc);

```



```
25 R1=Req/2;  
26 R2p=R1;  
27 X1=Xeq/2;  
28 X2p=X1;  
29 for i=1:3  
30     R2(i)=R2p(i)/TR(i)^2;  
31     X2(i)=X2p(i)/TR(i)^2;  
32 end  
33 %%  
34 Rc  
35 Xm  
36 R1  
37 X1  
38 R2  
39 X2
```

Appendix B

Microwave Oven Transformer

Characterization: *MATLAB* Code

```
1 %% Import data
2
3 clear all
4
5
6 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
7 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Lab Tests %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
8 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
9
10 MicroTestPath="ProvesTrafosMicro/";
11 MicroTestFnames=["20230503-0001.csv" "20230503-0002.csv"
12     "20230503-0003.csv" "20230503-0004.csv" "20230503-0005.csv"
13     "20230503-0006.csv" "20230503-0007.csv" "20230503-0008.csv"
14     "20230524-0001_Buit_T5.csv" "20230524-0002_CC_Trafo5.csv"
15     "20230524-0004_Buit_Trafo6.csv" "20230524-0003_CC_Trafo6.csv"];
16
17 for i=1:length(MicroTestFnames)
18     MicroTestFnames(i)=join([MicroTestPath, MicroTestFnames(i)], '');
19 end
20
21 DataSavingCompensation=1e-8;%Saving process double to int reverser
22 CurrentProbeConversion=1e-2;%100mV/A
23
24 VoltageProbeConversion=10;%100mV/V
```

```

20  Micro_Tests(1,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(1), 'Range', 'A3:A2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
      DataSavingCompensation; %temps
21  Micro_Tests(1,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(1), 'Range', 'B3:B2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
      VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
22  Micro_Tests(1,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(1), 'Range', 'C3:C2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
      CurrentProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
23
24  VoltageProbeConversion=10;%100mV/V
25  Micro_Tests(2,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(2), 'Range', 'A3:A2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
      DataSavingCompensation; %temps
26  Micro_Tests(2,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(2), 'Range', 'B3:B2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
      VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
27  Micro_Tests(2,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(2), 'Range', 'C3:C2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
      CurrentProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
28
29  VoltageProbeConversion=20;%50mV/V
30  Micro_Tests(3,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(3), 'Range', 'A3:A2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
      DataSavingCompensation; %temps
31  Micro_Tests(3,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(3), 'Range', 'B3:B2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
      VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
32  Micro_Tests(3,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(3), 'Range', 'C3:C2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
      CurrentProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
33
34  VoltageProbeConversion=10;%100mV/V
35  Micro_Tests(4,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(4), 'Range', 'A3:A2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
      DataSavingCompensation; %temps
36  Micro_Tests(4,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(4), 'Range', 'B3:B2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
      VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage

```

```

37 Micro_Tests(4,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(4), 'Range', 'C3:C2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
38
39 VoltageProbeConversion=20;%50mV/V
40 Micro_Tests(5,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(5), 'Range', 'A3:A2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
41 Micro_Tests(5,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(5), 'Range', 'B3:B2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
42 Micro_Tests(5,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(5), 'Range', 'C3:C2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
43
44 VoltageProbeConversion=20;%50mV/V
45 Micro_Tests(6,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(6), 'Range', 'A3:A2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
46 Micro_Tests(6,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(6), 'Range', 'B3:B2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
47 Micro_Tests(6,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(6), 'Range', 'C3:C2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
48
49 VoltageProbeConversion=20;%50mV/V
50 Micro_Tests(7,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(7), 'Range', 'A3:A2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
51 Micro_Tests(7,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(7), 'Range', 'B3:B2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
52 Micro_Tests(7,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(7), 'Range', 'C3:C2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
53
54 VoltageProbeConversion=20;%50mV/V

```

```

55 Micro_Tests(8,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(8), 'Range', 'A3:A2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
56 Micro_Tests(8,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(8), 'Range', 'B3:B2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
57 Micro_Tests(8,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(8), 'Range', 'C3:C2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
58
59 VoltageProbeConversion=2;%500mV/V
60 Micro_Tests(9,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(9), 'Range', 'A3:A2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
61 Micro_Tests(9,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(9), 'Range', 'B3:B2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
62 Micro_Tests(9,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(9), 'Range', 'C3:C2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
63
64 VoltageProbeConversion=2;%500mV/V
65 Micro_Tests(10,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(10), 'Range', 'A3:A2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
66 Micro_Tests(10,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(10), 'Range', 'B3:B2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
67 Micro_Tests(10,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(10), 'Range', 'C3:C2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
68
69 VoltageProbeConversion=2;%500mV/V
70 Micro_Tests(11,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(11), 'Range', 'A3:A2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
71 Micro_Tests(11,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroTestFnames(11), 'Range', 'B3:B2448', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage

```

```

72   Micro_Tests(11,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(11),'Range','C3:C2448','Delimiter',{' ';' }))))*
      CurrentProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
73
74   VoltageProbeConversion=2;%500mV/V
75   CurrentProbePolarityAdjust=-1;
76   Micro_Tests(12,1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(12),'Range','A3:A2448','Delimiter',{' ';' }))))*
      DataSavingCompensation; %temps
77   Micro_Tests(12,2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(12),'Range','B3:B2448','Delimiter',{' ';' }))))*
      VoltageProbeConversion*DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
78   Micro_Tests(12,3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
      MicroTestFnames(12),'Range','C3:C2448','Delimiter',{' ';' }))))*
      CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*CurrentProbeConversion*
      DataSavingCompensation; %Current
79
80   clear MicroTestFnames MicroTestPath i
81   save Micro_Tests
82   %%
83   %% Void & Short Circuit Tests Microwave Transformers
84
85   close all
86   clear all
87   for j=1:6 %Number of Transformers
88
89   load Micro_Tests.mat
90   %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
91   %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Open Circuit Test %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
92   %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
93
94   TR=[52.5/501 51.06/518.6 46.31/514.5 51.1/501 53.85/553.42
      49.87/553.3];
95   Tests=[1 2;3 4;5 8;6 7;9 10;11 12];
96   TestNum=Tests(j,1); %Transformer number j void test
97   exptime=Micro_Tests(TestNum,1,:);
98   exptime=reshape(exptime,1,[]);
99   Voltage=Micro_Tests(TestNum,2,:);
100  Voltage=reshape(Voltage,1,[]);

```

```

101 Current=Micro_Tests(TestNum,3,:);
102 Current=reshape(Current,1,[]);
103
104 VoidVoltage=Voltage;
105 VoidCurrent=Current;
106
107 VoidTestFig(j)=figure("Name",join(['Test ',int2str(TestNum),':
      Microwave Transformer T',int2str(j),' Void Test']));
108 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
109 grid on
110 hold on
111 yyaxis left
112 plot(exptime,Voltage,'b');
113 xlim([exptime(1) exptime(end)]);
114 xlabel("Time [ms]","FontSize",18);
115 ylabel("Voltage [V]","FontSize",18);
116 yyaxis right
117 plot(exptime,Current,'r');
118 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
119 legend("Primary Input Voltage ","Primary Input Current","FontSize",14)
      ;
120
121
122 for i=2:length(exptime)
123     deltaTimeSample(i-1)=exptime(i)-exptime(i-1);
124 end
125 PeriodeSample=mean(deltaTimeSample)*1e-3;%SamplePeriodMean [s]
126 Fs=1/PeriodeSample;%Samplefreq [Hz]
127 n=length(exptime);
128 f = Fs*(0:(n/2)+1)/n;
129
130 FSweepVoltage=fft(Voltage,n);
131 FSweepCurrent=fft(Current,n);
132 P2V = abs(FSweepVoltage/n);
133 P2C = abs(FSweepCurrent/n);
134 P1V = P2V(1:int64(n/2)+1);
135 P1V(2:end-1) = 2*P1V(2:end-1);
136 P1C = P2C(1:int64(n/2)+1);
137 P1C(2:end-1) = 2*P1C(2:end-1);

```

```

138 VoltHind=find(max(P1V)==P1V); %Find main voltage harmonic
139 CurrHind=find(max(P1C)==P1C); %Find main current harmonic
140 Vfreq0(j)=f(VoltHind);%Voltage frequency
141 Ifreq0(j)=f(CurrHind);%Current frequency
142 degreeOffsetVoid(j)=(angle(FSweepVoltage(VoltHind))-angle(
    FSweepCurrent(CurrHind)))*(360/(2*pi));%deg
143
144
145 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
146 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Short Circuit Test %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
147 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
148 TestNum=Tests(j,2); %Transformer number j SC test
149 exptime=Micro_Tests(TestNum,1,:);
150 exptime=reshape(exptime,1,[]);
151 Voltage=Micro_Tests(TestNum,2,:);
152 Voltage=reshape(Voltage,1,[]);
153 Current=Micro_Tests(TestNum,3,:);
154 Current=reshape(Current,1,[]);
155
156 SCVoltage=Voltage;
157 SCCurrent=Current;
158
159 SCTestFig(j)=figure("Name",join(['Test ',int2str(TestNum),': Microwave
    Transformer T',int2str(j),' Short Circuit Test']));
160 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
161 grid on
162 hold on
163 yyaxis left
164 plot(exptime,Voltage,'b');
165 xlim([exptime(1) exptime(end)]);
166 xlabel("Time [ms]","FontSize",18);
167 ylabel("Voltage [V]","FontSize",18);
168 yyaxis right
169 plot(exptime,Current,'r');
170 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
171 legend("Primary Input Voltage ","Primary Input Current","FontSize",14)
    ;
172
173 % Calculation

```

```

174
175     for i=2:length(exptime)
176         deltaTimeSample(i-1)=exptime(i)-exptime(i-1);
177     end
178     PeriodeSample=mean(deltaTimeSample)*1e-3;
179     Fs=1/PeriodeSample;
180     n=length(exptime);
181     f = Fs*(0:(n/2))/n;
182
183     FSweepVoltage=fft(Voltage,n);
184     FSweepCurrent=fft(Current,n);
185     P2V = abs(FSweepVoltage/n);
186     P2C = abs(FSweepCurrent/n);
187     P1V = P2V(1:int64(n/2)+1);
188     P1V(2:end-1) = 2*P1V(2:end-1);
189     P1C = P2C(1:int64(n/2)+1);
190     P1C(2:end-1) = 2*P1C(2:end-1);
191     VoltHind=find(max(P1V)==P1V);
192     CurrHind=find(max(P1C)==P1C);
193     VfreqSC(j)=f(VoltHind);
194     IfreqSC(j)=f(CurrHind);
195     degreeOffsetSC(j)=(angle(FSweepVoltage(VoltHind))-angle(FSweepCurrent(
196         CurrHind)))*(360/(2*pi));
197
198     % Calculation Simplified system
199
200     IOrms(j)=rms(VoidCurrent);
201     U0lv(j)=rms(VoidVoltage);
202     IOvect(j)=IOrms(j)*(cosd(-degreeOffsetVoid(j))+1i*sind(-
203         degreeOffsetVoid(j)));
204     S0(j)=U0lv(j)*(IOvect(j)');
205
206     P0(j)=real(S0(j));
207     Rc(j)=(U0lv(j)^2)/P0(j);
208     Xm(j)=(U0lv(j))^2/(sqrt((U0lv(j)*IOrms(j))^2-P0(j)^2));
209     Znucli(j)=S0(j)/(IOrms(j)^2);
210     Lm(j)=Xm(j)/(2*pi*Vfreq0(j));
211
212     Isc_rms(j)=rms(SCCurrent);

```

```

211     Usc_lv(j)=rms(SCVoltage);
212     Isc_vect(j)=Isc_rms(j)*(cosd(-degreeOffsetSC(j))+1i*sind(-
        degreeOffsetSC(j)));
213     S_sc_tot(j)=Usc_lv(j)*(Isc_vect(j)');
214     S_sc_nucli(j)=(Usc_lv(j)^2/Znucli(j)');
215     S_sc(j)=S_sc_tot(j)-S_sc_nucli(j);
216
217     Isc_nucli(j)=rms(Usc_lv(j)/Znucli(j)');
218
219     Isc_lv(j)=abs(S_sc(j)/Usc_lv(j));
220     Isc_hv(j)=Isc_lv(j)*TR(j);
221     Rsc_lv(j)=real(S_sc(j))/(Isc_lv(j)^2);
222     Xsc_lv(j)=imag(S_sc(j))/(Isc_lv(j)^2);
223
224     Z1_lv(j)=(Rsc_lv(j)/2)+1i*(Xsc_lv(j)/2);
225     Z2_lv(j)=Z1_lv(j);
226     Z2_hv(j)=Z2_lv(j)/TR(j)^2;
227     L1_lv(j)=imag(Z1_lv(j))/(2*pi*VfreqSC(j));
228     L2_lv(j)=imag(Z2_lv(j))/(2*pi*VfreqSC(j));
229     L2_hv(j)=L2_lv(j)/TR(j)^2;
230     Zpar_lv(j)=Znucli(j)*Z1_lv(j)/(Znucli(j)+Z1_lv(j));
231     Zoc_lv(j)=Z2_lv(j)+Znucli(j);
232     Zoc_hv(j)=Zoc_lv(j)/TR(j)^2;
233     Loc_hv(j)=imag(Zoc_hv(j))/(2*pi*VfreqSC(j));
234     Zt_lv(j)=Z2_lv(j)+Zpar_lv(j);
235     Zt_hv(j)=Zt_lv(j)/TR(j)^2;
236     Lt_hv(j)=imag(Zt_hv(j))/(2*pi*VfreqSC(j));
237     f_mains=50;%Hz
238     C_reso(j)=1/((2*pi*f_mains)^2*Lt_hv(j))*1e6;%uF
239 end
240 save ExpValues IOrms U0lv Isc_rms Usc_lv degreeOffsetVoid degreeOffsetSC
        Vfreq0 VfreqSC
241 save TValues TR Z1_lv L1_lv Rc Xm Lm Znucli Z2_lv Z2_hv L2_lv L2_hv
        Zpar_lv Zt_lv Zt_hv Lt_hv C_reso VoidTestFig SCTestFig

```

Appendix C

Picoscope Experimental Output: *MATLAB* Graph generator Code

```

1 clear all
2 close all
3 %% IMPORT DATA
4 clear all
5 %opts= detectImportOptions('Tensio_circuit_obert.csv','Range','A3:A100007
    ','Delimiter',{';'});
6 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
7 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Open Circuit %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
8 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
9 clear all
10 OpenCircuitPath="ProvesLaboAlta/OC/";
11 OCFnames=["20230310-0001_OC.csv" "20230310-0002.csv" "Tensio_circuit_obert
    .csv" ];
12 for i=1:length(OCFnames)
13     OCFnames(i)=join([OpenCircuitPath,OCFnames(i)], '');
14 end
15
16 DataSavingCompensation=1e-8;%Saving process double to int reverser
17
18 % Open Circuit Test 1
19 OC_Test1(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(OCFnames(1),'
    Range','A3:A100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*DataSavingCompensation; %
    temps

```

```

20 OC_Test1(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(OCFnames(1),'
    Range','B3:B100007','Delimiter',{' ';' }))))*DataSavingCompensation; %
    Voltage
21 % Open Circuit Test 2
22 OC_Test2(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(OCFnames(2),'
    Range','A3:A100007','Delimiter',{' ';' }))))*DataSavingCompensation; %
    temps
23 OC_Test2(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(OCFnames(2),'
    Range','B3:B100007','Delimiter',{' ';' }))))*DataSavingCompensation; %
    Voltage
24 % Open Circuit Test 3
25 OC_Test3(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(OCFnames(3),'
    Range','A3:A100007','Delimiter',{' ';' }))))*DataSavingCompensation; %
    temps
26 OC_Test3(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(OCFnames(3),'
    Range','B3:B100007','Delimiter',{' ';' }))))*DataSavingCompensation; %
    Voltage
27
28
29 %%
30
31 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
32 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Lab Tests C-Type Curve %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
33 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
34
35 CCurveTestPath="ProvesLaboAlta/CurveC/";
36 CCurveTestFnames=["prova1_interruptor.csv" "
    prova2_interruptor_mesura_corrent.csv" "prova3_mesura_corrent.csv" "
    prova4_corrent_fibra_carbomno.csv"];
37 for i=1:length(CCurveTestFnames)
38     CCurveTestFnames(i)=join([CCurveTestPath,CCurveTestFnames(i)], '');
39 end
40
41 CurrentProbeConversion=10;%100mV/A
42 CurrentProbePolarityAdjust=-1;
43 DataSavingCompensation=1e-8;%Saving process double to int reverser
44
45 % Test 1

```

```

46 C_Curve_Test1(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    C_Curve_TestFnames(1), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
47 C_Curve_Test1(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    C_Curve_TestFnames(1), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
48 % Test 2
49 C_Curve_Test2(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    C_Curve_TestFnames(2), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
50 C_Curve_Test2(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    C_Curve_TestFnames(2), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
51 C_Curve_Test2(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    C_Curve_TestFnames(2), 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
52 %Current Zeroing
53 [row,col] = find(C_Curve_Test2(1,:)>5);
54 CurrentZeroError=rms(C_Curve_Test2(3,col(1):end),"omitnan");
55 C_Curve_Test2(3,:)=C_Curve_Test2(3,:)+CurrentZeroError;
56 % Test 3
57 C_Curve_Test3(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    C_Curve_TestFnames(3), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
58 C_Curve_Test3(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    C_Curve_TestFnames(3), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
59 C_Curve_Test3(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    C_Curve_TestFnames(3), 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
60 %Current Zeroing
61 [row,col] = find(C_Curve_Test3(1,:)>5);
62 CurrentZeroError=rms(C_Curve_Test3(3,col(1):end),"omitnan");
63 C_Curve_Test3(3,:)=C_Curve_Test3(3,:)+CurrentZeroError;
64 % Test 4
65 C_Curve_Test1(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    C_Curve_TestFnames(4), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*

```

```

    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
66 C_Curve_Test1(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    C_Curve_TestFnames(4), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'})))*)
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
67 C_Curve_Test1(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    C_Curve_TestFnames(4), 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'})))*)
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
68 %Current Zeroing
69 [row,col] = find(C_Curve_Test1(1,:)>5);
70 CurrentZeroError=rms(C_Curve_Test1(3,col(1):end),"omitnan");
71 C_Curve_Test1(3,:)=C_Curve_Test1(3,:)+CurrentZeroError;
72
73 %%
74 clear all
75 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
76 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Lab Tests D-Type Curve %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
77 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
78
79 DCurveTestPath="ProvesLaboAlta/CurveD/";
80 DCurveTestFnames=["20230412_Prova1_Buit_D16.csv" "20230412_Prova2_D16_Buit
    .csv" "20230412_Prova3_fil_D16.csv" "20230412_Prova5_Choke_6mH_Fil_NiCr
    .csv" "20230412_Prova6_FibraCarbono_Choke_D16.csv" "20230412
    _Prova7_FilCoure_Choke.csv"];
81 for i=1:length(DCurveTestFnames)
82     DCurveTestFnames(i)=join([DCurveTestPath,DCurveTestFnames(i)], '');
83 end
84
85 CurrentProbeConversion=10;%100mV/A
86 CurrentProbePolarityAdjust=-1;
87 DataSavingCompensation=1e-8;%Saving process double to int reverser
88
89 % Test 1
90 D_Curve_Test1(1,:) = transpose(table2array(readtable(DCurveTestFnames(1), '
    Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))); %temps
91 D_Curve_Test1(2,:) = transpose(table2array(readtable(DCurveTestFnames(1), '
    Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))); %Voltage
92 D_Curve_Test1(3,:) = transpose(table2array(readtable(DCurveTestFnames(2), '
    Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))) * CurrentProbeConversion; %

```

```

    Current
93 %Current Zeroing
94     [row,col] = find(D_Curve_Test1(1,:)>5);
95     CurrentZeroError=rms(D_Curve_Test1(3,col(1):end),"omitnan");
96     D_Curve_Test1(3,:)=D_Curve_Test1(3,:)-CurrentZeroError;
97 % Test 2
98 D_Curve_Test2(1,:) = transpose(table2array(readtable(DCurveTestFnames(2),'
    Range','A3:A100007','Delimiter',{';'}))); %temps
99 D_Curve_Test2(2,:) = transpose(table2array(readtable(DCurveTestFnames(2),'
    Range','B3:B100007','Delimiter',{';'}))); %Voltage
100 D_Curve_Test2(3,:) = transpose(table2array(readtable(DCurveTestFnames(2),'
    Range','C3:C100007','Delimiter',{';'})))*CurrentProbeConversion; %
    Current
101 %Current Zeroing
102     [row,col] = find(D_Curve_Test2(1,:)>5);
103     CurrentZeroError=rms(D_Curve_Test2(3,col(1):end),"omitnan");
104     D_Curve_Test2(3,:)=D_Curve_Test2(3,:)-CurrentZeroError;
105 % Test 3
106 D_Curve_Test3(1,:) = transpose(table2array(readtable(DCurveTestFnames(3),'
    Range','A3:A100007','Delimiter',{';'}))); %temps
107 D_Curve_Test3(2,:) = transpose(table2array(readtable(DCurveTestFnames(3),'
    Range','B3:B100007','Delimiter',{';'}))); %Voltage
108 D_Curve_Test3(3,:) = transpose(table2array(readtable(DCurveTestFnames(3),'
    Range','C3:C100007','Delimiter',{';'})))*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust; %
    Current
109 %Current Zeroing
110     [row,col] = find(D_Curve_Test3(1,:)>5);
111     CurrentZeroError=rms(D_Curve_Test3(3,col(1):end),"omitnan");
112     D_Curve_Test3(3,:)=D_Curve_Test3(3,:)+CurrentZeroError;
113 % Test 4
114 D_Curve_Test4(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    DCurveTestFnames(4),'Range','A3:A100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
115 D_Curve_Test4(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    DCurveTestFnames(4),'Range','B3:B100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
116 D_Curve_Test4(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    DCurveTestFnames(4),'Range','C3:C100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
  
```



```

    _Test5_gap_vrtical_coure_dues_bobines.csv"];
146 for i=1:length(GenSetTestFnames)
147     GenSetTestFnames(i)=join([GenSetTestPath,GenSetTestFnames(i)], '');
148 end
149
150 CurrentProbeConversion=10;%100mV/A
151 CurrentProbePolarityAdjust=-1;
152 DataSavingCompensation=1e-8;%Saving process double to int reverser
153
154 % Test 1
155 GenSet_Test1(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
        GenSetTestFnames(1), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
        DataSavingCompensation; %temps
156 GenSet_Test1(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
        GenSetTestFnames(1), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
        DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
157 GenSet_Test1(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
        GenSetTestFnames(1), 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
        CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
        DataSavingCompensation; %Current
158 %Current Zeroing
159     [row,col] = find(GenSet_Test1(1, :)>5);
160     CurrentZeroError=rms(GenSet_Test1(3, col(1):end), "omitnan");
161     GenSet_Test1(3, :)=GenSet_Test1(3, :)+CurrentZeroError;
162 % Test 2
163 GenSet_Test2(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
        GenSetTestFnames(2), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
        DataSavingCompensation; %temps
164 GenSet_Test2(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
        GenSetTestFnames(2), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
        DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
165 GenSet_Test2(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
        GenSetTestFnames(2), 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
        CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
        DataSavingCompensation; %Current
166 %Current Zeroing
167     [row,col] = find(GenSet_Test2(1, :)>5);
168     CurrentZeroError=rms(GenSet_Test2(3, col(1):end), "omitnan");
169     GenSet_Test2(3, :)=GenSet_Test2(3, :)+CurrentZeroError;

```

```

170 % Test 3
171 GenSet_Test3(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    GenSetTestFnames(3), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
172 GenSet_Test3(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    GenSetTestFnames(3), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
173 GenSet_Test3(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    GenSetTestFnames(3), 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
174 %Current Zeroing
175 [row,col] = find(GenSet_Test3(1,*)>5);
176 CurrentZeroError=rms(GenSet_Test3(3,col(1):end),"omitnan");
177 GenSet_Test3(3,:)=GenSet_Test3(3,:)+CurrentZeroError;
178 % Test 4
179 GenSet_Test4(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    GenSetTestFnames(4), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
180 GenSet_Test4(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    GenSetTestFnames(4), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
181 GenSet_Test4(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    GenSetTestFnames(4), 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
182 %Current Zeroing
183 [row,col] = find(GenSet_Test4(1,*)>5);
184 CurrentZeroError=rms(GenSet_Test4(3,col(1):end),"omitnan");
185 GenSet_Test4(3,:)=GenSet_Test4(3,:)+CurrentZeroError;
186 % Test 5
187 GenSet_Test5(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    GenSetTestFnames(5), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
188 GenSet_Test5(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    GenSetTestFnames(5), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
189 GenSet_Test5(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    GenSetTestFnames(5), 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*

```

```

CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
DataSavingCompensation; %Current
190 %Current Zeroing
191 [row,col] = find(GenSet_Test5(1,:)>5);
192 CurrentZeroError=rms(GenSet_Test5(3,col(1):end),"omitnan");
193 GenSet_Test5(3,:)=GenSet_Test5(3,:)+CurrentZeroError;
194
195 %%
196 clear all
197 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
198 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Micro + Rectif Tests %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
199 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
200
201 MicroRectTestPath="ProvesMicrorectif/";
202 MicroRectTestFnames=["20230512-0001_125V.csv" "20230512-0002_125.csv"
    "20230512-0003_125V_corrent_T1.csv" "20230512-0004_125V_CorrentT1.csv"
    "20230512-0005_125V_Current_T3.csv" "20230512-0006_125V_Current_T3.csv"
    "20230512-0007_125V_Current_T4.csv" "20230512-0008_175V.csv"
    "20230512-0009_200V.csv"];
203 for i=1:length(MicroRectTestFnames)
204     MicroRectTestFnames(i)=join([MicroRectTestPath,MicroRectTestFnames(
        i)], '');
205 end
206
207 CurrentProbeConversion=10;%100mV/A
208 CurrentProbePolarityAdjust=1;
209 DataSavingCompensation=1e-8;%Saving process double to int reverser
210
211 % Test 1
212 MicroRect_Test1(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroRectTestFnames(1),'Range','A3:A100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
213 MicroRect_Test1(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroRectTestFnames(1),'Range','B3:B100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
214 MicroRect_Test1(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MicroRectTestFnames(1),'Range','C3:C100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
  
```

```
215
216 % Test 2
217 MicroRect_Test2(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(2), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
218 MicroRect_Test2(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(2), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
219 MicroRect_Test2(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(2), 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
220 % Test 3
221 MicroRect_Test3(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(3), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
222 MicroRect_Test3(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(3), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
223 MicroRect_Test3(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(3), 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
224 % Test 5
225 MicroRect_Test5(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(5), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
226 MicroRect_Test5(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(5), 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
227 MicroRect_Test5(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(5), 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
228 % Test 7
229 MicroRect_Test7(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(7), 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
```

```

230 MicroRect_Test7(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(7),'Range','B3:B100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
231 MicroRect_Test7(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(7),'Range','C3:C100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
232 % Test 8
233 MicroRect_Test8(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(8),'Range','A3:A100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
234 MicroRect_Test8(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(8),'Range','B3:B100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
235 MicroRect_Test8(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(8),'Range','C3:C100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
236 % Test 9
237 MicroRect_Test9(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(9),'Range','A3:A100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %temps
238 MicroRect_Test9(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(9),'Range','B3:B100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Voltage
239 MicroRect_Test9(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(
    MircroRectTestFnames(9),'Range','C3:C100007','Delimiter',{';'}))))*
    CurrentProbeConversion*CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*
    DataSavingCompensation; %Current
240
241
242 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
243 %% Open Circuit Test 1 Visualizer
244 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
245 close all
246 OCTest1_f1=figure("Name",'Open Circuit Test 1');
247 plot(OC_Test1(1,:),OC_Test1(2,:));
248 [row0,col0] = find(OC_Test1(1,*)>-1);
249 [row1,col1] = find(OC_Test1(1,*)<4);
  
```

```

250 xlim([OC_Test1(1,col0(1)) OC_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
251 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
252 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
253 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",18);
254 OCTest1_f2=figure("Name",'Open Circuit Test 1 Zoom In');
255 plot(OC_Test1(1,:),OC_Test1(2,:));
256 [row0,col0] = find(OC_Test1(1,*)>-0.1);
257 [row1,col1] = find(OC_Test1(1,*)<0.9);
258 xlim([OC_Test1(1,col0(1)) OC_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
259 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
260 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
261 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",18);
262 OCTest1_f3=figure("Name",'Open Circuit Test 1 Stable Zoom In');
263 plot(OC_Test1(1,:),OC_Test1(2,:),'-');
264 [row0,col0] = find(OC_Test1(1,*)>0.1);
265 [row1,col1] = find(OC_Test1(1,*)<0.2);
266 xlim([OC_Test1(1,col0(1)) OC_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
267 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
268 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
269 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",18);
270 %% Open Circuit Test 2 Visualizer
271 close all
272 OCTest2_f1=figure("Name",'Open Circuit Test 2');
273 plot(OC_Test2(1,:),OC_Test2(2,:));
274 [row0,col0] = find(OC_Test2(1,*)>-0.5);
275 [row1,col1] = find(OC_Test2(1,*)<2);
276 xlim([OC_Test2(1,col0(1)) OC_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
277 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
278 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
279 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",18);
280 OCTest2_f2=figure("Name",'Open Circuit Test 2 Zoom In');
281 plot(OC_Test2(1,:),OC_Test2(2,:));
282 [row0,col0] = find(OC_Test2(1,*)>-0.05);
283 [row1,col1] = find(OC_Test2(1,*)<0.5);
284 xlim([OC_Test2(1,col0(1)) OC_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
285 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
286 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
287 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",18);
288 OCTest2_f3=figure("Name",'Open Circuit Test 2 Stable Zoom In');

```

```

289 plot(OC_Test2(1,:),OC_Test2(2,:), '-');
290 [row0,col0] = find(OC_Test2(1,*)>0.1);
291 [row1,col1] = find(OC_Test2(1,*)<0.2);
292 xlim([OC_Test2(1,col0(1)) OC_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
293 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
294 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
295 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",18);
296 %% Open Circuit Test 3 Visualizer
297 close all
298 OCTest3_f1=figure("Name",'Open Circuit Test 3');
299 plot(OC_Test3(1,:),OC_Test3(2,:));
300 xlim([OC_Test3(1,1) OC_Test3(1,end)]);
301 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
302 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
303 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",18);
304 OCTest3_f2=figure("Name",'Open Circuit Test 3 Zoom In');
305 plot(OC_Test3(1,:),OC_Test3(2,:));
306 [row1,col1] = find(OC_Test3(1,*)<4);
307 xlim([OC_Test3(1,1) OC_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
308 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
309 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
310 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",18);
311 OCTest3_f3=figure("Name",'Open Circuit Test 3 Stable Zoom In');
312 plot(OC_Test3(1,:),OC_Test3(2,:), '-');
313 [row0,col0] = find(OC_Test3(1,*)>1.5);
314 [row1,col1] = find(OC_Test3(1,*)<1.6);
315 xlim([OC_Test3(1,col0(1)) OC_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
316 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
317 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
318 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",18);
319
320
321 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
322 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
323 %% C-Type Curve Test 1 Visulizer
324 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
325 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
326
327

```

```

328 close all
329 C_CurveT1f1=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 1');
330 plot(C_Curve_Test1(1,:),C_Curve_Test1(2,:), 'b');
331 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
332 xlim([C_Curve_Test1(1,1) C_Curve_Test1(1,end)]);
333 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
334 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
335 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14);
336 grid on
337 C_CurveT1f2=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 1 Zoom In');
338 plot(C_Curve_Test1(1,:),C_Curve_Test1(2,:), 'b');
339 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
340 [row0,col0] = find(C_Curve_Test1(1,:) > -0.1);
341 [row1,col1] = find(C_Curve_Test1(1,:) < 1);
342 xlim([C_Curve_Test1(1,col0(1)) C_Curve_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
343 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
344 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
345 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14);
346 grid on
347 C_CurveT1f3=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 1 Close up Zoom In');
348 plot(C_Curve_Test1(1,:),C_Curve_Test1(2,:), 'b');
349 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
350 [row0,col0] = find(C_Curve_Test1(1,:) > 0.73);
351 [row1,col1] = find(C_Curve_Test1(1,:) < 0.95);
352 xlim([C_Curve_Test1(1,col0(1)) C_Curve_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
353 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
354 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
355 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14);
356 grid on
357
358 %% C-Type Curve Test 2 Visulizer
359 close all
360 C_CurveT2f1=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 2');
361 hold on
362 yyaxis left
363 plot(C_Curve_Test2(1,:),C_Curve_Test2(2,:), 'b');
364 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
365 xlim([C_Curve_Test2(1,1) C_Curve_Test2(1,end)]);
366 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);

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367 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
368 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
369 grid on
370 yyaxis right
371 plot(C_Curve_Test2(1,:),C_Curve_Test2(3,:),'r');
372 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5); ylabel("Current [A]");
373 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
374 C_CurveT2f2=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 2 Zoom In');
375 hold on
376 yyaxis left
377 plot(C_Curve_Test2(1,:),C_Curve_Test2(2,:),'b');
378 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
379 [row0,col0] = find(C_Curve_Test2(1,:)>-0.1);
380 [row1,col1] = find(C_Curve_Test2(1,:)<1.3);
381 xlim([C_Curve_Test2(1,col0(1)) C_Curve_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
382 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
383 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
384 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
385 grid on
386 yyaxis right
387 plot(C_Curve_Test2(1,:),C_Curve_Test2(3,:),'r');
388 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
389 ylabel("Current [A]");
390 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","TextColor",'
      k');
391 C_CurveT1f3=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 2 Close up Zoom In');
392 plot(C_Curve_Test2(1,:),C_Curve_Test2(2,:),'b');
393 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
394 [row0,col0] = find(C_Curve_Test2(1,:)>1.02);
395 [row1,col1] = find(C_Curve_Test2(1,:)<1.1);
396 xlim([C_Curve_Test2(1,col0(1)) C_Curve_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
397 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
398 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
399 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
400 grid on
401 yyaxis right
402 plot(C_Curve_Test2(1,:),C_Curve_Test2(3,:),'r');
403 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5); ylabel("Current [A]");

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```

404 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
405 %% Proba 3 Corba C Visulizer
406 close all
407 C_CurveT3f1=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 3');
408 hold on
409 yyaxis left
410 plot(C_Curve_Test3(1,:),C_Curve_Test3(2,:),'b');
411 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
412 xlim([C_Curve_Test3(1,1) C_Curve_Test3(1,end)]);
413 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
414 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
415 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
416 grid on
417 yyaxis right
418 plot(C_Curve_Test3(1,:),C_Curve_Test3(3,:),'r');
419 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
420 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","TextColor",'
      k');
421 C_CurveT3f2=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 3 Zoom In');
422 hold on
423 yyaxis left
424 plot(C_Curve_Test3(1,:),C_Curve_Test3(2,:),'b');
425 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
426 [row0,col0] = find(C_Curve_Test3(1,:)>-0.1);
427 [row1,col1] = find(C_Curve_Test3(1,:)<1.5);
428 xlim([C_Curve_Test3(1,col0(1)) C_Curve_Test3(1,col1(end)]]);
429 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
430 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
431 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
432 grid on
433 yyaxis right
434 plot(C_Curve_Test3(1,:),C_Curve_Test3(3,:),'r');
435 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
436 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","TextColor",'
      k');
437 C_CurveT3f3=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 3 Close up Zoom In');
438 plot(C_Curve_Test3(1,:),C_Curve_Test3(2,:),'b');
439 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)

```

```

440 [row0,col0] = find(C_Curve_Test3(1,:)>1);
441 [row1,col1] = find(C_Curve_Test3(1,:)<1.2);
442 xlim([C_Curve_Test3(1,col0(1)) C_Curve_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
443 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
444 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
445 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
446 grid on
447 yyaxis right
448 plot(C_Curve_Test3(1,:),C_Curve_Test3(3:,:),'r');
449 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
450 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","TextColor",'
      k');
451 %% Proba 4 Corba C Visulizer
452 close all
453 C_CurveT4f1=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 4');
454 hold on
455 yyaxis left
456 plot(C_Curve_Test4(1,:),C_Curve_Test4(2:,:),'b');
457 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
458 xlim([C_Curve_Test4(1,1) C_Curve_Test4(1,end)]);
459 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
460 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
461 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
462 grid on
463 yyaxis right
464 plot(C_Curve_Test4(1,:),C_Curve_Test4(3:,:),'r');
465 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
466 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
467 C_CurveT4f2=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 4 Zoom In');
468 hold on
469 yyaxis left
470 plot(C_Curve_Test4(1,:),C_Curve_Test4(2:,:),'b');
471 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
472 [row0,col0] = find(C_Curve_Test4(1,:)>-0.1);
473 [row1,col1] = find(C_Curve_Test4(1,:)<0.3);
474 xlim([C_Curve_Test4(1,col0(1)) C_Curve_Test4(1,col1(end))]);
475 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
476 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);

```

```

477 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
478 grid on
479 yyaxis right
480 plot(C_Curve_Test4(1,:),C_Curve_Test4(3,:),'r');
481 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
482 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
483 C_CurveT4f3=figure("Name",'C-Type Curve Test 4 Close up Zoom In');
484 plot(C_Curve_Test4(1,:),C_Curve_Test4(2,:),'b');
485 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
486 [row0,col0] = find(C_Curve_Test4(1,:)>-0.05);
487 [row1,col1] = find(C_Curve_Test4(1,:)<0.05);
488 xlim([C_Curve_Test4(1,col0(1)) C_Curve_Test4(1,col1(end))]);
489 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
490 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
491 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
492 grid on
493 yyaxis right
494 plot(C_Curve_Test4(1,:),C_Curve_Test4(3,:),'r');
495 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);Test 1
496 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
497
498 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
499 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
500 %% D-Type Curve Test 1 Visulizer
501 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
502 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
503 close all
504 D_CurveT1f1=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 1');
505 hold on
506 yyaxis left
507 plot(D_Curve_Test1(1,:),D_Curve_Test1(2,:),'b');
508 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
509 xlim([D_Curve_Test1(1,1) D_Curve_Test1(1,end)]);
510 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
511 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
512 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
513 grid on
  
```

```

514 yyaxis right
515 plot(D_Curve_Test1(1,:),D_Curve_Test1(3,:), 'r');
516 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
517 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor", 'k');
518 D_CurveT1f2=figure("Name", 'D-Type Curve Test 1 Zoom In');
519 hold on
520 yyaxis left
521 plot(D_Curve_Test1(1,:),D_Curve_Test1(2,:), 'b');
522 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
523 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test1(1,:)>-0.1);
524 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test1(1,:)<0.3);
525 xlim([D_Curve_Test1(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
526 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
527 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
528 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor", 'k');
529 grid on
530 yyaxis right
531 plot(D_Curve_Test1(1,:),D_Curve_Test1(3,:), 'r');
532 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
533 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor", 'k');
534 D_CurveT1f3=figure("Name", 'D-Type Curve Test 1 Close up Zoom In');
535 plot(D_Curve_Test1(1,:),D_Curve_Test1(2,:), 'b');
536 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
537 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test1(1,:)>-0.05);
538 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test1(1,:)<0.05);
539 xlim([D_Curve_Test1(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
540 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
541 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
542 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor", 'k');
543 grid on
544 yyaxis right
545 plot(D_Curve_Test1(1,:),D_Curve_Test1(3,:), 'r');
546 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
547 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor", 'k');
548 %% Proba 2 Corba D Visulizer OC
549 close all

```

```

550 D_CurveT2f1=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 2');
551 hold on
552 yyaxis left
553 plot(D_Curve_Test2(1,:),D_Curve_Test2(2,),'b');
554 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
555 xlim([D_Curve_Test2(1,1) D_Curve_Test2(1,end)]);
556 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
557 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
558 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
559 grid on
560 yyaxis right
561 plot(D_Curve_Test2(1,:),D_Curve_Test2(3,),'r');
562 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
563 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
564 D_CurveT2f2=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 2 Zoom In');
565 hold on
566 yyaxis left
567 plot(D_Curve_Test2(1,:),D_Curve_Test2(2,),'b');
568 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
569 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test2(1,:)>-0.1);
570 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test2(1,:)<4);
571 xlim([D_Curve_Test2(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
572 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
573 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
574 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
575 grid on
576 yyaxis right
577 plot(D_Curve_Test2(1,:),D_Curve_Test2(3,),'r');
578 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
579 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
580 D_CurveT2f3=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 2 Close up Zoom In');
581 plot(D_Curve_Test2(1,:),D_Curve_Test2(2,),'b');
582 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
583 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test2(1,:)>-0.05);
584 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test2(1,:)<0.05);
585 xlim([D_Curve_Test2(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
586 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);

```

```

587 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
588 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
589 grid on
590 yyaxis right
591 plot(D_Curve_Test2(1,:),D_Curve_Test2(3,:),'r');
592 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
593 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
594 %% Proba 3 Corba D Visulizer      OK Test
595 close all
596 D_CurveT3f1=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 3');
597 hold on
598 yyaxis left
599 plot(D_Curve_Test3(1,:),D_Curve_Test3(2,:),'b');
600 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
601 xlim([D_Curve_Test3(1,1) D_Curve_Test3(1,end)]);
602 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
603 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
604 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
605 grid on
606 yyaxis right
607 plot(D_Curve_Test3(1,:),D_Curve_Test3(3,:),'r');
608 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
609 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
610 D_CurveT3f2=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 3 Zoom In');
611 hold on
612 yyaxis left
613 plot(D_Curve_Test3(1,:),D_Curve_Test3(2,:),'b');
614 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
615 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test3(1,:)>-0.1);
616 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test3(1,:)<0.3);
617 xlim([D_Curve_Test3(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
618 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
619 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
620 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
621 grid on
622 yyaxis right
623 plot(D_Curve_Test3(1,:),D_Curve_Test3(3,:),'r');

```

```

624 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
625 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
626 D_Curvef3=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 3 Close up Zoom In');
627 plot(D_Curve_Test3(1,:),D_Curve_Test3(2,),'b');
628 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
629 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test3(1,:) > -0.05);
630 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test3(1,:) < 0.05);
631 xlim([D_Curve_Test3(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
632 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
633 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
634 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
635 grid on
636 yyaxis right
637 plot(D_Curve_Test3(1,:),D_Curve_Test3(3,),'r');
638 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
639 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
640 %% Proba 4 Corba D Visulizer
641 close all
642 D_CurveT4f1=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 4');
643 hold on
644 yyaxis left
645 plot(D_Curve_Test4(1,:),D_Curve_Test4(2,),'b');
646 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
647 xlim([D_Curve_Test4(1,1) D_Curve_Test4(1,end)]);
648 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
649 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
650 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
651 grid on
652 yyaxis right
653 plot(D_Curve_Test4(1,:),D_Curve_Test4(3,),'r');
654 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
655 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
656 D_CurveT4f2=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 4 Zoom In');
657 hold on
658 yyaxis left
659 plot(D_Curve_Test4(1,:),D_Curve_Test4(2,),'b');

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```

660 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
661 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test4(1,:) > -0.1);
662 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test4(1,:) < 0.3);
663 xlim([D_Curve_Test4(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test4(1,col1(end))]);
664 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
665 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
666 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
667 grid on
668 yyaxis right
669 plot(D_Curve_Test4(1,:),D_Curve_Test4(3,),'r');
670 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
671 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
        ",14,"TextColor",'k');
672 D_CurveT4f3=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 4 Close up Zoom In');
673 plot(D_Curve_Test4(1,:),D_Curve_Test4(2,),'b');
674 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
675 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test4(1,:) > -0.05);
676 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test4(1,:) < 0.05);
677 xlim([D_Curve_Test4(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test4(1,col1(end))]);
678 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
679 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
680 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
681 grid on
682 yyaxis right
683 plot(D_Curve_Test4(1,:),D_Curve_Test4(3,),'r');
684 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
685 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
        ",14,"TextColor",'k');
686 %% Proba 5 Corba D Visulizer      OK Test
687 close all
688 D_CurveT5f1=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 5');
689 hold on
690 yyaxis left
691 plot(D_Curve_Test5(1,:),D_Curve_Test5(2,),'b');
692 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
693 xlim([D_Curve_Test5(1,1) D_Curve_Test5(1,end)]);
694 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
695 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
696 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');

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```

697 grid on
698 yyaxis right
699 plot(D_Curve_Test5(1,:),D_Curve_Test5(3,:), 'r');
700 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
701 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
702 D_CurveT5f2=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 5 Zoom In');
703 hold on
704 yyaxis left
705 plot(D_Curve_Test5(1,:),D_Curve_Test5(2,:), 'b');
706 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
707 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test5(1,:)>-0.1);
708 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test5(1,:)<0.3);
709 xlim([D_Curve_Test5(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test5(1,col1(end))]);
710 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
711 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
712 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
713 grid on
714 yyaxis right
715 plot(D_Curve_Test5(1,:),D_Curve_Test5(3,:), 'r');
716 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
717 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
718 D_CurveT5f3=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 5 Close up Zoom In');
719 plot(D_Curve_Test5(1,:),D_Curve_Test5(2,:), 'b');
720 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
721 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test5(1,:)>-0.05);
722 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test5(1,:)<0.05);
723 xlim([D_Curve_Test5(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test5(1,col1(end))]);
724 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
725 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
726 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
727 grid on
728 yyaxis right
729 plot(D_Curve_Test5(1,:),D_Curve_Test5(3,:), 'r');
730 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
731 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
732

```

```

733
734 %% Proba 6 Corba D Visulizer      OK Test
735 close all
736 D_CurveT6f1=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 6');
737 hold on
738 yyaxis left
739 plot(D_Curve_Test6(1,:),D_Curve_Test6(2:3,:), 'b');
740 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
741 xlim([D_Curve_Test6(1,1) D_Curve_Test6(1,end)]);
742 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
743 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
744 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
745 grid on
746 yyaxis right
747 plot(D_Curve_Test6(1,:),D_Curve_Test6(3,:), 'r');
748 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
749 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
750 D_CurveT6f2=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 6 Zoom In');
751 hold on
752 yyaxis left
753 plot(D_Curve_Test6(1,:),D_Curve_Test6(2:3,:), 'b');
754 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
755 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test6(1,:) > -0.1);
756 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test6(1,:) < 0.3);
757 xlim([D_Curve_Test6(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test6(1,col1(end))]);
758 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
759 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
760 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
761 grid on
762 yyaxis right
763 plot(D_Curve_Test6(1,:),D_Curve_Test6(3,:), 'r');
764 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
765 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
766 D_CurveT6f3=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 6 Close up Zoom In');
767 plot(D_Curve_Test6(1,:),D_Curve_Test6(2:3,:), 'b');
768 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
769 [row0,col0] = find(D_Curve_Test6(1,:) > -0.05);

```

```

770 [row1,col1] = find(D_Curve_Test6(1,:) < 0.05);
771 xlim([D_Curve_Test6(1,col0(1)) D_Curve_Test6(1,col1(end))]);
772 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
773 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
774 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
775 grid on
776 yyaxis right
777 plot(D_Curve_Test6(1,:),D_Curve_Test6(3,),'r');
778 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
779 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
780
781
782
783
784 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
785 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
786 %% GenSet Test 1 Visulizer
787 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
788 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
789 close all
790 GenSetT1f1=figure("Name",'GenSet Test 1');
791 hold on
792 grid on
793 yyaxis left
794 plot(GenSet_Test1(1,:),GenSet_Test1(2,),'b');
795 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
796 xlim([GenSet_Test1(1,1) GenSet_Test1(1,end)]);
797 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
798 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
799 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
800 yyaxis right
801 plot(GenSet_Test1(1,:),GenSet_Test1(3,),'r');
802 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
803 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
804 GenSetT1f2=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 1 Zoom In');
805 hold on
806 grid on
  
```

```

807 yyaxis left
808 plot(GenSet_Test1(1,:),GenSet_Test1(2,:), 'b');
809 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
810 [row0,col0] = find(GenSet_Test1(1,*)>-0.1);
811 [row1,col1] = find(GenSet_Test1(1,*)<4);
812 xlim([GenSet_Test1(1,col0(1)) GenSet_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
813 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
814 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
815 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor","k");
816 yyaxis right
817 plot(GenSet_Test1(1,:),GenSet_Test1(3,:), 'r');
818 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
819 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor","k");
820 GenSetT1f3=figure("Name","D-Type Curve Test 1 Close up Zoom In");
821 hold on
822 grid on
823 yyaxis left
824 plot(GenSet_Test1(1,:),GenSet_Test1(2,:), 'b');
825 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
826 [row0,col0] = find(GenSet_Test1(1,*)>-0.05);
827 [row1,col1] = find(GenSet_Test1(1,*)<0.05);
828 xlim([GenSet_Test1(1,col0(1)) GenSet_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
829 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
830 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
831 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor","k");
832 yyaxis right
833 plot(GenSet_Test1(1,:),GenSet_Test1(3,:), 'r');
834 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
835 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor","k");
836
837 %% GenSet Test 2 Visulizer
838 close all
839 GenSetT2f1=figure("Name","GenSet Test 2");
840 hold on
841 grid on
842 yyaxis left
843 plot(GenSet_Test2(1,:),GenSet_Test2(2,:), 'b');

```

```

844 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
845 xlim([GenSet_Test2(1,1) GenSet_Test2(1,end)]);
846 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
847 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
848 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
849 yyaxis right
850 plot(GenSet_Test2(1,:),GenSet_Test2(3:,:), 'r');
851 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
852 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
853 GenSetT2f2=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 2 Zoom In');
854 hold on
855 grid on
856 yyaxis left
857 plot(GenSet_Test2(1,:),GenSet_Test2(2:,:), 'b');
858 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
859 [row0,col0] = find(GenSet_Test2(1,:) > -0.1);
860 [row1,col1] = find(GenSet_Test2(1,:) < 1.5);
861 xlim([GenSet_Test2(1,col0(1)) GenSet_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
862 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
863 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
864 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
865 yyaxis right
866 plot(GenSet_Test2(1,:),GenSet_Test2(3:,:), 'r');
867 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
868 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
869 GenSetT2f3=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 2 Close up Zoom In');
870 hold on
871 grid on
872 yyaxis left
873 plot(GenSet_Test2(1,:),GenSet_Test2(2:,:), 'b');
874 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
875 [row0,col0] = find(GenSet_Test2(1,:) > 1.15);
876 [row1,col1] = find(GenSet_Test2(1,:) < 1.45);
877 xlim([GenSet_Test2(1,col0(1)) GenSet_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
878 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
879 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
880 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');

```

```

881 yyaxis right
882 plot(GenSet_Test2(1,:),GenSet_Test2(3:),'r');
883 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
884 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
885
886 %% GenSet Test 3 Visulizer
887 close all
888 GenSetT3f1=figure("Name",'GenSet Test 3');
889 hold on
890 grid on
891 yyaxis left
892 plot(GenSet_Test3(1,:),GenSet_Test3(2:),'b');
893 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
894 xlim([GenSet_Test3(1,1) GenSet_Test3(1,end)]);
895 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
896 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
897 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
898 yyaxis right
899 plot(GenSet_Test3(1,:),GenSet_Test3(3:),'r');
900 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
901 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
902 GenSetT3f2=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 3 Zoom In');
903 hold on
904 grid on
905 yyaxis left
906 plot(GenSet_Test3(1,:),GenSet_Test3(2:),'b');
907 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
908 [row0,col0] = find(GenSet_Test3(1,:)>-0.1);
909 [row1,col1] = find(GenSet_Test3(1,:)<1.3);
910 xlim([GenSet_Test3(1,col0(1)) GenSet_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
911 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
912 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
913 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
914 yyaxis right
915 plot(GenSet_Test3(1,:),GenSet_Test3(3:),'r');
916 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);

```

```

917 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
918 GenSetT3f3=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 3 Close up Zoom In');
919 hold on
920 grid on
921 yyaxis left
922 plot(GenSet_Test3(1,:),GenSet_Test3(2,:), 'b');
923 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
924 [row0,col0] = find(GenSet_Test3(1,*)>0.9);
925 [row1,col1] = find(GenSet_Test3(1,*)<1.3);
926 xlim([GenSet_Test3(1,col0(1)) GenSet_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
927 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
928 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
929 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
930 yyaxis right
931 plot(GenSet_Test3(1,:),GenSet_Test3(3,:), 'r');
932 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
933 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
934
935 %% GenSet Test 4 Visulizer
936 close all
937 GenSetT4f1=figure("Name",'GenSet Test 4');
938 hold on
939 grid on
940 yyaxis left
941 plot(GenSet_Test4(1,:),GenSet_Test4(2,:), 'b');
942 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
943 xlim([GenSet_Test4(1,1) GenSet_Test4(1,end)]);
944 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
945 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
946 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
947 yyaxis right
948 plot(GenSet_Test4(1,:),GenSet_Test4(3,:), 'r');
949 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
950 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
951 GenSetT4f2=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 4 Zoom In');
952 hold on

```

```

953 grid on
954 yyaxis left
955 plot(GenSet_Test4(1,:),GenSet_Test4(2,:), 'b');
956 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
957 [row0,col0] = find(GenSet_Test4(1,:)>-0.1);
958 [row1,col1] = find(GenSet_Test4(1,:)<1.3);
959 xlim([GenSet_Test4(1,col0(1)) GenSet_Test4(1,col1(end))]);
960 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
961 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
962 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
963 yyaxis right
964 plot(GenSet_Test4(1,:),GenSet_Test4(3,:), 'r');
965 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
966 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
967 GenSetT4f3=figure("Name",'D-Type Curve Test 4 Close up Zoom In');
968 hold on
969 grid on
970 yyaxis left
971 plot(GenSet_Test4(1,:),GenSet_Test4(2,:), 'b');
972 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
973 [row0,col0] = find(GenSet_Test4(1,:)>0.9);
974 [row1,col1] = find(GenSet_Test4(1,:)<1.3);
975 xlim([GenSet_Test4(1,col0(1)) GenSet_Test4(1,col1(end))]);
976 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
977 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
978 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
979 yyaxis right
980 plot(GenSet_Test4(1,:),GenSet_Test4(3,:), 'r');
981 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
982 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
983
984 %% GenSet Test 5 Visulizer
985 close all
986 GenSetT5f1=figure("Name",'GenSet Test 5');
987 hold on
988 grid on
989 yyaxis left
  
```

```

990 plot(GenSet_Test5(1,:),GenSet_Test5(2,:), 'b');
991 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
992 xlim([GenSet_Test5(1,1) GenSet_Test5(1,end)]);
993 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
994 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
995 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor", 'k');
996 yyaxis right
997 plot(GenSet_Test5(1,:),GenSet_Test5(3,:), 'r');
998 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
999 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor", 'k');
1000 GenSetT5f2=figure("Name", 'D-Type Curve Test 5 Zoom In');
1001 hold on
1002 grid on
1003 yyaxis left
1004 plot(GenSet_Test5(1,:),GenSet_Test5(2,:), 'b');
1005 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1006 [row0,col0] = find(GenSet_Test5(1,:)>-0.1);
1007 [row1,col1] = find(GenSet_Test5(1,:)<1.3);
1008 xlim([GenSet_Test5(1,col0(1)) GenSet_Test5(1,col1(end))]);
1009 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1010 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1011 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor", 'k');
1012 yyaxis right
1013 plot(GenSet_Test5(1,:),GenSet_Test5(3,:), 'r');
1014 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1015 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor", 'k');
1016 GenSetT5f3=figure("Name", 'D-Type Curve Test 5 Close up Zoom In');
1017 hold on
1018 grid on
1019 yyaxis left
1020 plot(GenSet_Test5(1,:),GenSet_Test5(2,:), 'b');
1021 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1022 [row0,col0] = find(GenSet_Test5(1,:)>0.75);
1023 [row1,col1] = find(GenSet_Test5(1,:)<1.1);
1024 xlim([GenSet_Test5(1,col0(1)) GenSet_Test5(1,col1(end))]);
1025 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1026 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);

```

```

1027 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1028 yyaxis right
1029 plot(GenSet_Test5(1,:),GenSet_Test5(3:,:),'r');
1030 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1031 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1032
1033 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
1034 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
1035 %% MicroArc Test 1 Visulizer
1036 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
1037 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
1038 close all
1039 MicroRectT1f1=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 1')
      ;
1040 hold on
1041 grid on
1042 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1043 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1044 yyaxis left
1045 plot(MicroRect_Test1(1,:),MicroRect_Test1(2:,:),'b');
1046 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1047 xlim([MicroRect_Test1(1,1) MicroRect_Test1(1,end)]);
1048 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1049 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1050 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1051 yyaxis right
1052 plot(MicroRect_Test1(1,:),MicroRect_Test1(3:,:),'r');
1053 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1054 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1055 %
1056 MicroRectT1f2=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 1
      Arc 1 Zoom In');
1057 hold on
1058 grid on
1059 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1060 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1061 yyaxis left
  
```

```

1062 plot(MicroRect_Test1(1,:),MicroRect_Test1(2,:), 'b');
1063 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1064 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test1(1,:)>-0.2);
1065 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test1(1,:)<1.7);
1066 xlim([MicroRect_Test1(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
1067 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1068 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1069 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1070 yyaxis right
1071 plot(MicroRect_Test1(1,:),MicroRect_Test1(3,:), 'r');
1072 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1073 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1074 highcurrlim=5;%highlimit
1075 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1076 %
1077 MicroRectT1f4=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 1
    Arc 1 Close up Zoom In');
1078 hold on
1079 grid on
1080 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1081 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1082 yyaxis left
1083 plot(MicroRect_Test1(1,:),MicroRect_Test1(2,:), 'b');
1084 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1085 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test1(1,:)>0.7);%lowlimit
1086 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test1(1,:)<0.9);%highlimit
1087 xlim([MicroRect_Test1(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
1088 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1089 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1090 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1091 highvoltlim=1;%highlimit
1092 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1093 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1094 yyaxis right
1095 plot(MicroRect_Test1(1,:),MicroRect_Test1(3,:), 'r');
1096 lowcurrlim=1.5;%lowlimit
1097 highcurrlim=4.5;%highlimit
1098 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
  
```

```

1099 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1100 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1101 %
1102 MicroRectT1f5=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 1
      Arc 2 Zoom In');
1103 hold on
1104 grid on
1105 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1106 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1107 yyaxis left
1108 plot(MicroRect_Test1(1,:),MicroRect_Test1(2,:),'b');
1109 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1110 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test1(1,:)>6.5);
1111 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test1(1,:)<8.7);
1112 xlim([MicroRect_Test1(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test1(1,col1(end))]);
1113 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1114 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1115 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1116 yyaxis right
1117 plot(MicroRect_Test1(1,:),MicroRect_Test1(3,:),'r');
1118 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1119 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1120 highcurrlim=5;%highlimit
1121 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1122 %
1123 MicroRectT1f3=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 1
      Arc 2 Close up Zoom In');
1124 hold on
1125 grid on
1126 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1127 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1128 yyaxis left
1129 plot(MicroRect_Test1(1,:),MicroRect_Test1(2,:),'b');
1130 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1131 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test1(1,:)>7.5);%lowlimit
1132 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test1(1,:)<8);%highlimit
1133 xlim([MicroRect_Test1(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test1(1,col1(end))]);

```

```

1134 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1135 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1136 lowvoltlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1137 highvoltlim=2.5;%highlimit
1138 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1139 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1140 yyaxis right
1141 plot(MicroRect_Test1(1,:),MicroRect_Test1(3,:),'r');
1142 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1143 highcurrlim=3.5;%highlimit
1144 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1145 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1146 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1147
1148 %% MicroArc Test 2 Visulizer
1149 close all
1150 MicroRectT2f1=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 2')
      ;
1151 hold on
1152 grid on
1153 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1154 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1155 yyaxis left
1156 plot(MicroRect_Test2(1,:),MicroRect_Test2(2,:),'b');
1157 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1158 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test2(1,:) < 11);
1159 xlim([MicroRect_Test2(1,1) MicroRect_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
1160 %xlim([MicroRect_Test2(1,1) MicroRect_Test2(1,end)]);
1161 %xlim([MicroRect_Test2(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
1162 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1163 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1164 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1165 yyaxis right
1166 plot(MicroRect_Test2(1,:),MicroRect_Test2(3,:),'r');
1167 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1168 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1169 %

```

```

1170 MicroRectT2f2=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 2
      Arc 1 Zoom In');
1171 hold on
1172 grid on
1173 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1174 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1175 yyaxis left
1176 plot(MicroRect_Test2(1,:),MicroRect_Test2(2,:), 'b');
1177 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1178 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test2(1,:)>-0.1);
1179 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test2(1,:)<1);
1180 xlim([MicroRect_Test2(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
1181 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1182 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1183 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1184 yyaxis right
1185 plot(MicroRect_Test2(1,:),MicroRect_Test2(3,:), 'r');
1186 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1187 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1188 highcurrlim=4;%highlimit
1189 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1190 %
1191 MicroRectT2f4=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 2
      Arc 1 Close up Zoom In');
1192 hold on
1193 grid on
1194 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1195 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1196 yyaxis left
1197 plot(MicroRect_Test2(1,:),MicroRect_Test2(2,:), 'b');
1198 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1199 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test2(1,:)>0.3);%lowlimit
1200 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test2(1,:)<0.9);%highlimit
1201 xlim([MicroRect_Test2(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
1202 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1203 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1204 lowvoltlim=-2;%lowlimit
1205 highvoltlim=2;%highlimit

```

```

1206 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1207 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1208 yyaxis right
1209 plot(MicroRect_Test2(1,:),MicroRect_Test2(3,:), 'r');
1210 lowcurrlim=1.2;%lowlimit
1211 highcurrlim=4.5;%highlimit
1212 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1213 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1214 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1215 %
1216 MicroRectT2f5=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 2
      Arc 2 Zoom In');
1217 hold on
1218 grid on
1219 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1220 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1221 yyaxis left
1222 plot(MicroRect_Test2(1,:),MicroRect_Test2(2,:), 'b');
1223 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1224 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test2(1,:)>6.9);%lowlimit
1225 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test2(1,:)<8.7);%highlimit
1226 xlim([MicroRect_Test2(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
1227 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1228 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1229 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1230 highvoltlim=4;%highlimit
1231 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1232 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1233 yyaxis right
1234 plot(MicroRect_Test2(1,:),MicroRect_Test2(3,:), 'r');
1235 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1236 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1237 highcurrlim=5;%highlimit
1238 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1239 %
1240 MicroRectT2f6=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 2
      Arc 2 Close up Zoom In');

```

```

1241 hold on
1242 grid on
1243 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1244 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1245 yyaxis left
1246 plot(MicroRect_Test2(1,:),MicroRect_Test2(2,:), 'b');
1247 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1248 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test2(1,:)>7.5);%lowlimit
1249 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test2(1,:)<8);%highlimit
1250 xlim([MicroRect_Test2(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test2(1,col1(end))]);
1251 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1252 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1253 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1254 highvoltlim=2.5;%highlimit
1255 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1256 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1257 yyaxis right
1258 plot(MicroRect_Test2(1,:),MicroRect_Test2(3,:), 'r');
1259 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1260 highcurrlim=3.5;%highlimit
1261 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1262 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1263 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1264
1265 %% MicroArc Test 3 Visulizer
1266 close all
1267 MicroRectT3f1=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 3')
    ;
1268 hold on
1269 grid on
1270 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1271 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1272 yyaxis left
1273 plot(MicroRect_Test3(1,:),MicroRect_Test3(2,:), 'b');
1274 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1275 lowvoltlim=-1.2;%lowlimit
1276 highvoltlim=4;%highlimit
1277 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);

```

```

1278 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test3(1,:) < 10);
1279 xlim([MicroRect_Test3(1,1) MicroRect_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
1280 %xlim([MicroRect_Test3(1,1) MicroRect_Test3(1,end)]);
1281 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1282 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1283 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1284 yyaxis right
1285 lowcurrlim=-4;%lowlimit
1286 highcurrlim=10;%highlimit
1287 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1288 plot(MicroRect_Test3(1,:),MicroRect_Test3(3,:),'r');
1289 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1290 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1291 %
1292 %
1293 %
1294 MicroRectT3f2=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 3
      Arc 1 Zoom In');
1295 hold on
1296 grid on
1297 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1298 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1299 yyaxis left
1300 plot(MicroRect_Test3(1,:),MicroRect_Test3(2,:),'b');
1301 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1302 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test3(1,:) > -0.1);
1303 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test3(1,:) < 0.7);
1304 xlim([MicroRect_Test3(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
1305 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1306 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1307 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1308 yyaxis right
1309 plot(MicroRect_Test3(1,:),MicroRect_Test3(3,:),'r');
1310 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1311 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1312 highcurrlim=4;%highlimit
1313 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');

```

```

1314 %
1315 %
1316 %
1317 MicroRectT3f3=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 3
      Arc 1 Close up Zoom In');
1318 hold on
1319 grid on
1320 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1321 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1322 yyaxis left
1323 plot(MicroRect_Test3(1,:),MicroRect_Test3(2,),'b');
1324 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1325 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test3(1,:)>0.3);%lowlimit
1326 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test3(1,:)<0.5);%highlimit
1327 xlim([MicroRect_Test3(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
1328 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1329 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1330 lowvoltlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1331 highvoltlim=2;%highlimit
1332 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1333 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1334 yyaxis right
1335 plot(MicroRect_Test3(1,:),MicroRect_Test3(3,),'r');
1336 lowcurrlim=-4;%lowlimit
1337 highcurrlim=4;%highlimit
1338 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1339 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1340 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1341 %
1342 MicroRectT3f4=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 3
      Arc 2 Zoom In');
1343 hold on
1344 grid on
1345 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1346 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1347 yyaxis left
1348 plot(MicroRect_Test3(1,:),MicroRect_Test3(2,),'b');
1349 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)

```

```

1350 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test3(1,:) > 2.8);%lowlimit
1351 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test3(1,:) < 4);%highlimit
1352 xlim([MicroRect_Test3(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
1353 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1354 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1355 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1356 highvoltlim=4;%highlimit
1357 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1358 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1359 yyaxis right
1360 plot(MicroRect_Test3(1,:),MicroRect_Test3(3,:),'r');
1361 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1362 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1363 highcurrlim=5;%highlimit
1364 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1365 %
1366 MicroRectT3f5=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 3
      Arc 2 Close up Zoom In');
1367 hold on
1368 grid on
1369 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1370 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1371 yyaxis left
1372 plot(MicroRect_Test3(1,:),MicroRect_Test3(2,:),'b');
1373 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1374 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test3(1,:) > 3);%lowlimit
1375 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test3(1,:) < 3.2);%highlimit
1376 xlim([MicroRect_Test3(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test3(1,col1(end))]);
1377 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1378 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1379 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1380 highvoltlim=1.5;%highlimit
1381 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1382 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1383 yyaxis right
1384 plot(MicroRect_Test3(1,:),MicroRect_Test3(3,:),'r');
1385 lowcurrlim=-3.5;%lowlimit
1386 highcurrlim=3.5;%highlimit

```

```

1387 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1388 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1389 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1390
1391 %% MicroArc Test 5 Visulizer
1392 close all
1393 MicroRectT5f1=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 5')
      ;
1394 hold on
1395 grid on
1396 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1397 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1398 yyaxis left
1399 plot(MicroRect_Test5(1,:),MicroRect_Test5(2,:),'b');
1400 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1401 lowvoltlim=-1.2;%lowlimit
1402 highvoltlim=4;%highlimit
1403 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1404 % [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test5(1,:)<10);
1405 % xlim([MicroRect_Test5(1,1) MicroRect_Test5(1,col1(end))]);
1406 xlim([MicroRect_Test5(1,1) MicroRect_Test5(1,end)]);
1407 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1408 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1409 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1410 yyaxis right
1411 lowcurrlim=-4;%lowlimit
1412 highcurrlim=10;%highlimit
1413 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1414 plot(MicroRect_Test5(1,:),MicroRect_Test5(3,:),'r');
1415 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1416 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1417 %
1418 %
1419 %
1420 MicroRectT5f2=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 5
      Arc 1 Zoom In');
1421 hold on

```

```

1422 grid on
1423 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1424 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1425 yyaxis left
1426 plot(MicroRect_Test5(1,:),MicroRect_Test5(2,:), 'b');
1427 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1428 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test5(1,:) > -0.1);
1429 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test5(1,:) < 2);
1430 xlim([MicroRect_Test5(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test5(1,col1(end))]);
1431 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1432 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1433 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor","k");
1434 yyaxis right
1435 plot(MicroRect_Test5(1,:),MicroRect_Test5(3,:), 'r');
1436 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1437 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1438 highcurrlim=4;%highlimit
1439 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor","k");
1440 %
1441 %
1442 %
1443 MicroRectT5f3=figure("Name","Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 5
    Arc 1 Close up Zoom In");
1444 hold on
1445 grid on
1446 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1447 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1448 yyaxis left
1449 plot(MicroRect_Test5(1,:),MicroRect_Test5(2,:), 'b');
1450 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1451 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test5(1,:) > 0.3);%lowlimit
1452 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test5(1,:) < 0.5);%highlimit
1453 xlim([MicroRect_Test5(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test5(1,col1(end))]);
1454 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1455 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1456 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1457 highvoltlim=1.5;%highlimit
1458 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);

```

```

1459 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1460 yyaxis right
1461 plot(MicroRect_Test5(1,:),MicroRect_Test5(3,:),'r');
1462 lowcurrlim=-5;%lowlimit
1463 highcurrlim=5;%highlimit
1464 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1465 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1466 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1467 %
1468 MicroRectT5f4=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 5
      Arc 2 Zoom In');
1469 hold on
1470 grid on
1471 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1472 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1473 yyaxis left
1474 plot(MicroRect_Test5(1,:),MicroRect_Test5(2,:),'b');
1475 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1476 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test5(1,:)>9);%lowlimit
1477 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test5(1,:)<12);%highlimit
1478 xlim([MicroRect_Test5(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test5(1,col1(end))]);
1479 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1480 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1481 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1482 highvoltlim=4;%highlimit
1483 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1484 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1485 yyaxis right
1486 plot(MicroRect_Test5(1,:),MicroRect_Test5(3,:),'r');
1487 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1488 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1489 highcurrlim=5;%highlimit
1490 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1491 %
1492 MicroRectT5f5=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 5
      Arc 2 Close up Zoom In');
1493 hold on
  
```

```

1494 grid on
1495 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1496 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1497 yyaxis left
1498 plot(MicroRect_Test5(1,:),MicroRect_Test5(2,:), 'b');
1499 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1500 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test5(1,:)>10);%lowlimit
1501 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test5(1,:)<10.5);%highlimit
1502 xlim([MicroRect_Test5(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test5(1,col1(end))]);
1503 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1504 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1505 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1506 highvoltlim=1.5;%highlimit
1507 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1508 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1509 yyaxis right
1510 plot(MicroRect_Test5(1,:),MicroRect_Test5(3,:), 'r');
1511 lowcurrlim=-4;%lowlimit
1512 highcurrlim=4;%highlimit
1513 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1514 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1515 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1516
1517 %% MicroArc Test 7 Visulizer
1518 close all
1519 MicroRectT7f1=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 7')
      ;
1520 hold on
1521 grid on
1522 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1523 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1524 yyaxis left
1525 plot(MicroRect_Test7(1,:),MicroRect_Test7(2,:), 'b');
1526 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1527 lowvoltlim=-1.2;%lowlimit
1528 highvoltlim=4;%highlimit
1529 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1530 % [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test7(1,:)<10);

```

```

1531 % xlim([MicroRect_Test7(1,1) MicroRect_Test7(1,col1(end))]);
1532 xlim([MicroRect_Test7(1,1) MicroRect_Test7(1,end)]);
1533 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1534 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1535 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1536 yyaxis right
1537 lowcurrlim=-4;%lowlimit
1538 highcurrlim=10;%highlimit
1539 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1540 plot(MicroRect_Test7(1,:),MicroRect_Test7(3,:), 'r');
1541 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1542 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1543 %
1544 %
1545 %
1546 MicroRectT7f2=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 7
      Arc 1 Zoom In');
1547 hold on
1548 grid on
1549 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1550 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1551 yyaxis left
1552 plot(MicroRect_Test7(1,:),MicroRect_Test7(2,:), 'b');
1553 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1554 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test7(1,:)>-0.1);
1555 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test7(1,:)<1);
1556 xlim([MicroRect_Test7(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test7(1,col1(end))]);
1557 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1558 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1559 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1560 yyaxis right
1561 plot(MicroRect_Test7(1,:),MicroRect_Test7(3,:), 'r');
1562 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1563 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1564 highcurrlim=4;%highlimit
1565 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1566 %

```

```

1567 %
1568 %
1569 MicroRectT7f3=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 7
      Arc 1 Close up Zoom In');
1570 hold on
1571 grid on
1572 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1573 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1574 yyaxis left
1575 plot(MicroRect_Test7(1,:),MicroRect_Test7(2,:), 'b');
1576 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1577 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test7(1,:)>0.3);%lowlimit
1578 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test7(1,:)<0.5);%highlimit
1579 xlim([MicroRect_Test7(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test7(1,col1(end))]);
1580 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1581 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1582 lowvolttlim=-1;%lowlimit
1583 highvolttlim=1.5;%highlimit
1584 ylim([lowvolttlim highvolttlim]);
1585 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1586 yyaxis right
1587 plot(MicroRect_Test7(1,:),MicroRect_Test7(3,:), 'r');
1588 lowcurrlim=-5;%lowlimit
1589 highcurrlim=5;%highlimit
1590 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1591 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1592 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1593 %
1594 MicroRectT7f4=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 7
      Arc 2 Zoom In');
1595 hold on
1596 grid on
1597 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1598 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1599 yyaxis left
1600 plot(MicroRect_Test7(1,:),MicroRect_Test7(2,:), 'b');
1601 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1602 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test7(1,:)>15.8);%lowlimit

```

```

1603 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test7(1,:) < 17.8); %highlimit
1604 xlim([MicroRect_Test7(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test7(1,col1(end))]);
1605 xlabel("Time [s]", "FontSize", 18);
1606 ylabel("Voltage [kV]", "FontSize", 18);
1607 lowvoltlim = -1; %lowlimit
1608 highvoltlim = 4; %highlimit
1609 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1610 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage", "FontSize", 14, "TextColor", 'k');
1611 yyaxis right
1612 plot(MicroRect_Test7(1,:), MicroRect_Test7(3,:), 'r');
1613 ylabel("Current [A]", "FontSize", 18);
1614 lowcurrlim = -0.5; %lowlimit
1615 highcurrlim = 5; %highlimit
1616 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage", "Capacitor Output Current", "FontSize",
1617        ", 14, "TextColor", 'k');
1618 %
1619 MicroRectT7f5 = figure("Name", 'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 7
1620        Arc 2 Close up Zoom In');
1621 hold on
1622 grid on
1623 set(gca, 'XMinorGrid', 'on');
1624 set(gca, 'YMinorGrid', 'on');
1625 yyaxis left
1626 plot(MicroRect_Test7(1,:), MicroRect_Test7(2,:), 'b');
1627 set(gca, "FontSize", 12.5)
1628 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test7(1,:) > 17); %lowlimit
1629 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test7(1,:) < 17.5); %highlimit
1630 xlim([MicroRect_Test7(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test7(1,col1(end))]);
1631 xlabel("Time [s]", "FontSize", 18);
1632 ylabel("Voltage [kV]", "FontSize", 18);
1633 lowvoltlim = -0.5; %lowlimit
1634 highvoltlim = 1.5; %highlimit
1635 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1636 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage", "FontSize", 14, "TextColor", 'k');
1637 yyaxis right
1638 plot(MicroRect_Test7(1,:), MicroRect_Test7(3,:), 'r');
1639 lowcurrlim = -4; %lowlimit
1640 highcurrlim = 4; %highlimit
1641 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);

```

```

1640 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1641 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Capacitor Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1642
1643 %% MicroArc Test 8 Visulizer
1644 close all
1645 MicroRectT8f1=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 8')
      ;
1646 hold on
1647 grid on
1648 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1649 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1650 yyaxis left
1651 plot(MicroRect_Test8(1,:),MicroRect_Test8(2,),'b');
1652 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1653 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test8(1,:)<11);
1654 xlim([MicroRect_Test8(1,1) MicroRect_Test8(1,col1(end))]);
1655 %xlim([MicroRect_Test8(1,1) MicroRect_Test8(1,end)]);
1656 %xlim([MicroRect_Test8(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test8(1,col1(end))]);
1657 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1658 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1659 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1660 yyaxis right
1661 plot(MicroRect_Test8(1,:),MicroRect_Test8(3,),'r');
1662 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1663 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1664 %
1665 MicroRectT8f2=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 8
      Arc 1 Zoom In');
1666 hold on
1667 grid on
1668 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1669 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1670 yyaxis left
1671 plot(MicroRect_Test8(1,:),MicroRect_Test8(2,),'b');
1672 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1673 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test8(1,:)>-0.1);
1674 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test8(1,:)<0.9);

```

```

1675 xlim([MicroRect_Test8(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test8(1,col1(end))]);
1676 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1677 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1678 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1679 yyaxis right
1680 plot(MicroRect_Test8(1,:),MicroRect_Test8(3,:), 'r');
1681 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1682 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1683 highcurrlim=4;%highlimit
1684 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1685 %
1686 MicroRectT8f3=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 8
      Arc 1 Close up Zoom In');
1687 hold on
1688 grid on
1689 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1690 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1691 yyaxis left
1692 plot(MicroRect_Test8(1,:),MicroRect_Test8(2,:), 'b');
1693 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1694 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test8(1,:)>0.1);%lowlimit
1695 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test8(1,:)<0.5);%highlimit
1696 xlim([MicroRect_Test8(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test8(1,col1(end))]);
1697 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1698 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1699 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1700 highvoltlim=2;%highlimit
1701 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1702 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1703 yyaxis right
1704 plot(MicroRect_Test8(1,:),MicroRect_Test8(3,:), 'r');
1705 lowcurrlim=-1;%lowlimit
1706 highcurrlim=6;%highlimit
1707 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1708 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1709 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1710 %

```

```

1711 MicroRectT8f4=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 8
      Arc 2 Zoom In');
1712 hold on
1713 grid on
1714 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1715 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1716 yyaxis left
1717 plot(MicroRect_Test8(1,:),MicroRect_Test8(2,:), 'b');
1718 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1719 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test8(1,:)>7.4);%lowlimit
1720 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test8(1,:)<8.4);%highlimit
1721 xlim([MicroRect_Test8(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test8(1,col1(end))]);
1722 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1723 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1724 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1725 highvoltlim=4;%highlimit
1726 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1727 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1728 yyaxis right
1729 plot(MicroRect_Test8(1,:),MicroRect_Test8(3,:), 'r');
1730 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1731 % lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1732 % highcurrlim=5;%highlimit
1733 % ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1734 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1735 %
1736 MicroRectT8f5=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 8
      Arc 2 Close up Zoom In');
1737 hold on
1738 grid on
1739 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1740 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1741 yyaxis left
1742 plot(MicroRect_Test8(1,:),MicroRect_Test8(2,:), 'b');
1743 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1744 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test8(1,:)>7.5);%lowlimit
1745 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test8(1,:)<8);%highlimit
1746 xlim([MicroRect_Test8(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test8(1,col1(end))]);

```

```

1747 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1748 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1749 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1750 highvoltlim=2;%highlimit
1751 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1752 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1753 yyaxis right
1754 plot(MicroRect_Test8(1,:),MicroRect_Test8(3,:),'r');
1755 lowcurrlim=-1;%lowlimit
1756 highcurrlim=5.2;%highlimit
1757 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1758 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1759 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1760
1761 %% MicroArc Test 9 Visulizer
1762 close all
1763 MicroRectT9f1=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 9')
      ;
1764 hold on
1765 grid on
1766 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1767 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1768 yyaxis left
1769 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(2,:),'b');
1770 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1771 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test9(1,:)<11);
1772 xlim([MicroRect_Test9(1,1) MicroRect_Test9(1,col1(end))]);
1773 %xlim([MicroRect_Test9(1,1) MicroRect_Test9(1,end)]);
1774 %xlim([MicroRect_Test9(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test9(1,col1(end))]);
1775 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1776 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1777 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1778 yyaxis right
1779 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(3,:),'r');
1780 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1781 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1782 %

```

```

1783 MicroRectT9f2=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 9
      Arc 1 Zoom In');
1784 hold on
1785 grid on
1786 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1787 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1788 yyaxis left
1789 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(2,),'b');
1790 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1791 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test9(1,*)>2.5);
1792 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test9(1,*)<4.7);
1793 xlim([MicroRect_Test9(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test9(1,col1(end))]);
1794 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1795 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1796 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1797 yyaxis right
1798 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(3,),'r');
1799 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1800 lowcurrlim=-0.5;%lowlimit
1801 highcurrlim=4;%highlimit
1802 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1803 %
1804 MicroRectT9f3=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 9
      Arc 1 Close up Zoom In');
1805 hold on
1806 grid on
1807 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1808 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1809 yyaxis left
1810 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(2,),'b');
1811 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1812 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test9(1,*)>0.1);%lowlimit
1813 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test9(1,*)<0.5);%highlimit
1814 xlim([MicroRect_Test9(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test9(1,col1(end))]);
1815 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1816 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1817 lowvoltlim=-1;%lowlimit
1818 highvoltlim=3;%highlimit

```

```

1819 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1820 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1821 yyaxis right
1822 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(3,:), 'r');
1823 lowcurrlim=-1;%lowlimit
1824 highcurrlim=6;%highlimit
1825 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1826 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1827 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1828 %
1829 MicroRectT9f4=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 9
      Arc 2 Zoom In');
1830 hold on
1831 grid on
1832 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1833 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1834 yyaxis left
1835 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(2,:), 'b');
1836 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1837 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test9(1,:)>7);%lowlimit
1838 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test9(1,:)<8);%highlimit
1839 xlim([MicroRect_Test9(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test9(1,col1(end))]);
1840 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1841 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1842 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1843 yyaxis right
1844 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(3,:), 'r');
1845 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1846 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
1847 %
1848 MicroRectT9f5=figure("Name",'Resonating Transformers Arc Attempts Test 9
      Arc 2 Close up Zoom In');
1849 hold on
1850 grid on
1851 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
1852 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
1853 yyaxis left

```

```

1854 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(2,:), 'b');
1855 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
1856 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test9(1,:)>7.2);%lowlimit
1857 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test9(1,:)<7.5);%highlimit
1858 xlim([MicroRect_Test9(1,col0(1)) MicroRect_Test9(1,col1(end))]);
1859 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
1860 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
1861 lowvoltlim=-2;%lowlimit
1862 highvoltlim=2;%highlimit
1863 ylim([lowvoltlim highvoltlim]);
1864 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","FontSize",14,"TextColor",'k');
1865 yyaxis right
1866 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(3,:), 'r');
1867 lowcurrlim=-1;%lowlimit
1868 highcurrlim=7;%highlimit
1869 ylim([lowcurrlim highcurrlim]);
1870 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
1871 legend("Rectifier Output Voltage","Rectifier Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');

```

Appendix D

Microwave Oven Transformer Simulation Model Calculation: *MATLAB* Code

```

1 %% Data for Void Simulations
2
3 clear all
4 load TValues;
5 load ExpValues;
6 close all
7 Un=230;
8 TransformerNum=6
9 Uin=U0lv(TransformerNum)
10 fin=Vfreq0(TransformerNum)
11 U2n=Un/TR(TransformerNum)*1e-3%kV
12 R1=real(Z1_lv(TransformerNum))
13 R2=real(Z2_hv(TransformerNum))
14 L1=L1_lv(TransformerNum)*1e3% mH
15 L2=L2_hv(TransformerNum)*1e3% mH
16 Zm=abs(Znucli(TransformerNum))
17 I0peak=sqrt(2)*Un/abs(Znucli(TransformerNum))
18 F0=sqrt(2)*230/(2*pi*50)
19 %Primary Saturation
20 Ua=U0lv(TransformerNum)
21 Ia=I0rms(TransformerNum)

```

```

22 Ub=Un
23 Ib=abs(Un/(Z1_lv(TransformerNum)+Znucli(TransformerNum)))
24 %% Data for SC Simulations
25
26 clear all
27 load TValues;
28 load ExpValues;
29 close all
30 Un=230;
31 TransformerNum=4
32 Uin=Usc_lv(TransformerNum)
33 fin=VfreqSC(TransformerNum)
34 U2n=Un/TR(TransformerNum)*1e-3%kV
35 R1=real(Z1_lv(TransformerNum))
36 R2=real(Z2_hv(TransformerNum))
37 L1=L1_lv(TransformerNum)*1e3%MH
38 L2=L2_hv(TransformerNum)*1e3%MH
39 Zm=abs(Znucli(TransformerNum))
40 IOpeak=sqrt(2)*Un/abs(Znucli(TransformerNum))
41 F0=sqrt(2)*230/(2*pi*50)
42 %Primary Saturation
43 Ua=U0lv(TransformerNum)
44 Ia=IOrms(TransformerNum)
45 Ub=Un
46 Ib=abs(Un/(Z1_lv(TransformerNum)+Znucli(TransformerNum)))
47 %% Import Sim data comparison (ATP)
48
49 clear all
50 load ExpValues.mat
51
52 %Open Circuit Sims
53 load Tests\VoidTestsSim2.mat
54
55 IOSim(:,1)=reshape(iT1S1,1,[]);
56 IOSim(:,2)=reshape(iT2S2,1,[]);
57 IOSim(:,3)=reshape(iT3S3,1,[]);
58 IOSim(:,4)=reshape(iT4S4,1,[]);
59 IOSim(:,5)=reshape(iT5S5,1,[]);
60 IOSim(:,6)=reshape(iT6S6,1,[]);

```

```

61
62 UOSim(:,1)=reshape(vT1,1,[]);
63 UOSim(:,2)=reshape(vT2,1,[]);
64 UOSim(:,3)=reshape(vT3,1,[]);
65 UOSim(:,4)=reshape(vT4,1,[]);
66 UOSim(:,5)=reshape(vT5,1,[]);
67 UOSim(:,6)=reshape(vT6,1,[]);
68
69 IOSim_rms=rms(IOSim)
70 UOSim_rms=rms(UOSim)
71
72 for i=2:length(t)
73     deltaTimeSample(i-1)=t(i)-t(i-1);
74 end
75 PeriodeSample=mean(deltaTimeSample);
76 Fs=1/PeriodeSample;
77
78 n=length(t);
79 f = Fs*(0:(n/2))/n;
80 FSweepVoltage=fft(UOSim,n);
81 FSweepCurrent=fft(IOSim,n);
82 P2V = abs(FSweepVoltage/n);
83 P2C = abs(FSweepCurrent/n);
84 P1V = P2V(1:int64(n/2)+1,:);
85 P1V(2:end-1,:) = 2*P1V(2:end-1,:);
86 P1C = P2C(1:int64(n/2)+1,:);
87 P1C(2:end-1,:) = 2*P1C(2:end-1,:);
88 for j=1:6
89     VoltHind(j)=find(max(P1V(:,j))==P1V(:,j));
90     CurrHind(j)=find(max(P1C(:,j))==P1C(:,j));
91     f(VoltHind(j));
92     f(CurrHind(j));
93     angle(FSweepVoltage(:,j))*(360/(2*pi));
94     angle(FSweepCurrent(:,j))*(360/(2*pi));
95     degOffsetVoidSim(j)=(angle(FSweepVoltage(VoltHind(j),j))-angle(
        FSweepCurrent(CurrHind(j),j)))*(360/(2*pi));
96 end
97 degOffsetVoidSim;
98

```

```

99 %SC Sims
100 load Tests\SCTestsSim2.mat
101
102 IscSim(:,1)=reshape(iT1S1,1,[]);
103 IscSim(:,2)=reshape(iT2S2,1,[]);
104 IscSim(:,3)=reshape(iT3S3,1,[]);
105 IscSim(:,4)=reshape(iT4S4,1,[]);
106 IscSim(:,5)=reshape(iT5S5,1,[]);
107 IscSim(:,6)=reshape(iT6S6,1,[]);
108
109 UscSim(:,1)=reshape(vT1,1,[]);
110 UscSim(:,2)=reshape(vT2,1,[]);
111 UscSim(:,3)=reshape(vT3,1,[]);
112 UscSim(:,4)=reshape(vT4,1,[]);
113 UscSim(:,5)=reshape(vT5,1,[]);
114 UscSim(:,6)=reshape(vT6,1,[]);
115
116 IscSim_rms=rms(IscSim)
117 UscSim_rms=rms(UscSim)
118
119 for i=2:length(t)
120     deltaTimeSample(i-1)=t(i)-t(i-1);
121 end
122 PeriodeSample=mean(deltaTimeSample);
123 Fs=1/PeriodeSample;
124
125 n=length(t);
126 f = Fs*(0:(n/2))/n;
127 FSweepVoltage=fft(U0Sim,n);
128 FSweepCurrent=fft(I0Sim,n);
129 P2V = abs(FSweepVoltage/n);
130 P2C = abs(FSweepCurrent/n);
131 P1V = P2V(1:int64(n/2)+1,:);
132 P1V(2:end-1,:) = 2*P1V(2:end-1,:);
133 P1C = P2C(1:int64(n/2)+1,:);
134 P1C(2:end-1,:) = 2*P1C(2:end-1,:);
135 for j=1:6
136     VoltHind(j)=find(max(P1V(:,j))==P1V(:,j));
137     CurrHind(j)=find(max(P1C(:,j))==P1C(:,j));

```

```

138     f(VoltHind(j));
139     f(CurrHind(j));
140     angle(FSweepVoltage(:,j))*(360/(2*pi));
141     angle(FSweepCurrent(:,j))*(360/(2*pi));
142     degOffsetSCSim(j)=(angle(FSweepVoltage(VoltHind(j),j))-angle(
        FSweepCurrent(CurrHind(j),j)))*(360/(2*pi));
143 end
144 degOffsetSCSim;
145
146 %Error Calculation
147 for j=1:6
148 ErrVoltVoidrms(j)=100*(U0Sim_rms(j)-U0lv(j))/U0lv(j);%p100
149 ErrCurrVoidrms(j)=100*(I0Sim_rms(j)-I0rms(j))/I0rms(j);
150 ErrVoltSCrms(j)=100*(UscSim_rms(j)-Usc_lv(j))/Usc_lv(j);
151 ErrCurrSCrms(j)=100*(IscSim_rms(j)-Isc_rms(j))/Isc_rms(j);
152 end
153
154 ErrVoltVoidrms
155 ErrCurrVoidrms
156 ErrVoltSCrms
157 ErrCurrSCrms

```

Appendix E

Microwave Oven Transformer

Characterization: ATPDraw Model

Values

Figure E.1: Transformer Model used: ATPDraw's Saturable 1-Phase Transformer

Figure E.2: Microwave Oven Transformer 1 Model Values: Part A

Figure E.3: Microwave Oven Transformer 1 Model Values: Part B

Figure E.4: Microwave Oven Transformer 2 Model Values: Part A

Figure E.5: Microwave Oven Transformer 2 Model Values: Part B

Figure E.6: Microwave Oven Transformer 3 Model Values: Part A

Figure E.7: Microwave Oven Transformer 3 Model Values: Part B

Figure E.8: Microwave Oven Transformer 4 Model Values: Part A

Figure E.9: Microwave Oven Transformer 4 Model Values: Part B

Figure E.10: Microwave Oven Transformer 5 Model Values: Part A

Figure E.11: Microwave Oven Transformer 5 Model Values: Part B

Figure E.12: Microwave Oven Transformer 6 Model Values: Part A

Figure E.13: Microwave Oven Transformer 6 Model Values: Part B

Appendix F

Simulation Model Graph Comparison: *MATLAB* Code

```

1 clear all
2 close all
3 TestPath="Real/20230512-0009_200V.csv";
4
5 CurrentProbeConversion=10;%100mV/A
6 CurrentProbePolarityAdjust=1;
7 DataSavingCompensation=1e-8;%Saving process double to int reverser
8 %syncro 0.9955
9 % Test 9
10 MicroRect_Test9(1,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(TestPath
    , 'Range', 'A3:A100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*DataSavingCompensation+1.4;
    %temps
11 MicroRect_Test9(2,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(TestPath
    , 'Range', 'B3:B100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*DataSavingCompensation; %
    Voltage
12 MicroRect_Test9(3,:) = str2double(transpose(table2array(readtable(TestPath
    , 'Range', 'C3:C100007', 'Delimiter', {';'}))))*CurrentProbeConversion*
    CurrentProbePolarityAdjust*DataSavingCompensation; %Current
13 clear TestPath CurrentProbeConversion CurrentProbePolarityAdjust
    DataSavingCompensation
14 %% Load Static R Sim
15 load Sim\Test9Sim.mat
16 IgapSim(1,:)=iDcposGappos.';
17 tSim(1,:)=t.';

```

```

18 VDCSim(1,:)=vDcposDcneg.*1e-3;%kV
19 clear t iDcposGappos vDcposDcneg
20
21 %% Void Comparison
22 close all
23 f1=figure("Name",'Void Comparison Sim vs Experiment');
24 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(2:,:),'b')
25 hold on
26 plot(tSim,VDCSim,'r')
27 xlim([0.8 1.5])
28 ylim([-2 4])
29 grid on
30 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
31 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
32 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
33 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
34 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
35 legend("Experiment Output Voltage","Simulation Output Voltage","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
36 f2=figure("Name",'Void Comparison Sim vs Experiment Close up');
37 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(2:,:),'b')
38 hold on
39 plot(tSim,VDCSim,'r')
40 xlim([0.8 0.9])
41 ylim([2.4 3.1])
42 grid on
43 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
44 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
45 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
46 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
47 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
48 legend("Experiment Output Voltage","Simulation Output Voltage","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
49
50 %% Void Error Calculation
51 upperlimR = find(MicroRect_Test9(1,:)>1.3);
52 upperlimS = find(tSim(1,:)>1.3);
53 Vrealrms=rms(MicroRect_Test9(2,1:upperlimR(1)))
54 VSimrms=rms(VDCSim(1:upperlimS(1)))

```

```

55 Err=(VSimrms-Vrealrms)*100/Vrealrms
56 %%
57 close all
58 f1=figure("Name",'Arc Comparison Static R Sim vs Experiment');
59 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(2,:), 'b')
60 hold on
61 plot(tSim,VDCSim, 'r')
62 xlim([1.3 2.12])
63 ylim([-2 4])
64 grid on
65 set(gca, 'XMinorGrid', 'on');
66 set(gca, 'YMinorGrid', 'on');
67 set(gca, "FontSize", 12.5)
68 xlabel("Time [s]", "FontSize", 18);
69 ylabel("Voltage [kV]", "FontSize", 18);
70 legend("Experiment Output Voltage", "Simulation Output Voltage", "FontSize
    ", 14, "TextColor", 'k');
71 f2=figure("Name",'Arc Comparison Static R Sim vs Experiment Close up');
72 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(2,:), 'b')
73 hold on
74 plot(tSim,VDCSim, 'r')
75 xlim([1.36 1.56])
76 ylim([-2 4])
77 grid on
78 set(gca, 'XMinorGrid', 'on');
79 set(gca, 'YMinorGrid', 'on');
80 set(gca, "FontSize", 12.5)
81 xlabel("Time [s]", "FontSize", 18);
82 ylabel("Voltage [kV]", "FontSize", 18);
83 legend("Experiment Output Voltage", "Simulation Output Voltage", "FontSize
    ", 14, "TextColor", 'k');
84
85 %% Current
86 close all
87 f1=figure("Name",'Arc Comparison Static R Sim vs Experiment');
88 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(3,:), 'b')
89 hold on
90 plot(tSim,IgapSim, 'r')
91 xlim([1.3 2.12])

```

```

92 %ylim([-2 4])
93 grid on
94 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
95 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
96 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
97 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
98 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
99 legend("Experiment Output Current","Simulation Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
100 f2=figure("Name",'Arc Comparison Static R Sim vs Experiment Close up');
101 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(3:,:),'b')
102 hold on
103 plot(tSim,IgapSim,'r')
104 xlim([1.36 1.56])
105 %ylim([-2 4])
106 grid on
107 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
108 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
109 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
110 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
111 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
112 legend("Experiment Output Current","Simulation Output Current","FontSize
    ",14,"TextColor",'k');
113 %%
114 clc
115 clear Comb Comb2 Comb3
116 close all
117 for i=1:length(MicroRect_Test9(1,:))
118 Rgap(i)=MicroRect_Test9(2,i)*1e3/MicroRect_Test9(3,i);
119 end
120 movRMS=dsp.MovingRMS(80);
121 Rgaprms=movRMS(Rgap. ');
122
123 Comb(:,1)=MicroRect_Test9(1,:);
124 Comb(:,2)=Rgaprms;
125
126 %plot(Comb(:,1),Comb(:,2))
127 %plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),Rgaprms)
128

```

```

129 [row0,col0] = find(MicroRect_Test9(:,1)>0);%lowlimit
130 [row1,col1] = find(MicroRect_Test9(:,1)<0.7);%highlimit
131 xlim([0 0.7]);
132 %Comb(row0:row1,1) 10658
133 Comb2=Comb(7042:12291,:);
134 l=length(Comb2)/30;
135 for i=1:30 %Resample (30 samples in total)
136     Comb3(i,2)=rms(Comb2(1+(i-1)*l:i*l,2),"omitnan");
137     Comb3(i,1)=Comb2(1+(i-1)*l+fix(l/2),1);
138 end
139 %plot(Comb2(:,1),Comb2(:,2))
140 plot(Comb3(:,1),Comb3(:,2))
141 xlim([Comb3(1,1) 2.1])
142 grid on
143 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
144 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
145 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
146 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
147 ylabel("Arc Resistance [Ohm]","FontSize",18);
148 %% Load Dynamic R Sim
149 load Sim\Test9SimRDynamic.mat
150 IgapSim(1,:)=iDcposGappos.';
151 tSim(1,:)=t.';
152 VDCSim(1,:)=vDcposDcneg.*1e-3;%kV
153 clear t iDcposGappos vDcposDcneg
154 %% Voltage
155 close all
156 f1=figure("Name",'Arc Comparison Dynamic R Sim vs Experiment');
157 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(2,:),'b')
158 hold on
159 plot(tSim,VDCSim,'r')
160 xlim([1.3 2.2])
161 ylim([-2 4])
162 grid on
163 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
164 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
165 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
166 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
167 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);

```

```

168 legend("Experiment Output Voltage","Simulation Output Voltage","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
169 f2=figure("Name",'Arc Comparison Dynamic R Sim vs Experiment Close up');
170 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(2,:),'b')
171 hold on
172 plot(tSim,VDCSim,'r')
173 xlim([1.36 1.56])
174 ylim([-2 4])
175 grid on
176 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
177 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
178 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
179 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
180 ylabel("Voltage [kV]","FontSize",18);
181 legend("Experiment Output Voltage","Simulation Output Voltage","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
182 %% Current
183 close all
184 f1=figure("Name",'Arc Comparison Dynamic R Sim vs Experiment');
185 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(3,:),'b')
186 hold on
187 plot(tSim,IgapSim,'r')
188 xlim([1.3 2.12])
189 %ylim([-2 4])
190 grid on
191 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
192 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
193 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
194 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
195 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
196 legend("Experiment Output Current","Simulation Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
197 f2=figure("Name",'Arc Comparison Dynamic R Sim vs Experiment Close up');
198 plot(MicroRect_Test9(1,:),MicroRect_Test9(3,:),'b')
199 hold on
200 plot(tSim,IgapSim,'r')
201 xlim([1.36 1.56])
202 %ylim([-2 4])
203 grid on

```

```
204 set(gca,'XMinorGrid','on');
205 set(gca,'YMinorGrid','on');
206 set(gca,"FontSize",12.5)
207 xlabel("Time [s]","FontSize",18);
208 ylabel("Current [A]","FontSize",18);
209 legend("Experiment Output Current","Simulation Output Current","FontSize
      ",14,"TextColor",'k');
```

Appendix G

Centralized Control Unit PCB Images

Figure G.1

Figure G.2

Figure G.3

Figure G.4

Figure G.5

Title	Number	Revision
A4		

Date: 1/07/2024
 File: X:\Universitat\1_Reviseurs\3_SchDoc
 Sheet of: 4
 Drawn By:

Figure G.6

Appendix H

Remote Control PCB Images

Figure H.1

Figure H.2

Figure H.3

Figure H.4

Figure H.5

Figure H.6

Appendix I

Arc Experiments Photos

I.1 Test 5 - 175V - Arc 1

Figure I.1: Arc Frame 1

Figure I.2: Arc Frame 2

Figure I.3: Arc Frame 3

Figure I.4: Arc Frame 4

Figure I.5: Arc Frame 5

Figure I.6: Arc Frame 6

Figure I.7: Arc Frame 7

Figure I.8: Arc Frame 8

Figure I.9: Arc Frame 9

Figure I.10: Arc Frame 10

Figure I.11: Arc Frame 11

Figure I.12: Arc Frame 12

Figure I.13: Arc Frame 13

Figure I.14: Arc Frame 14

Figure I.15: Arc Frame 15

Figure I.16: Arc Frame 16

Figure I.17: Arc Frame 17

Figure I.18: Arc Frame 18

Figure I.19: Arc Frame 19

Figure I.20: Arc Frame 20

Figure I.21: Arc Frame 21

Figure I.22: Arc Frame 22

Figure I.23: Arc Frame 23

Figure I.24: Arc Frame 24

Figure I.25: Arc Frame 25

Figure I.26: Arc Frame 26

Figure I.27: Arc Frame 27

Figure I.28: Arc Frame 28

Figure I.29: Arc Frame 29

Figure I.30: Arc Frame 30

Figure I.31: Arc Frame 31

I.2 Test 5 - 175V - Arc 2

Figure I.32: Arc Frame 1

Figure I.33: Arc Frame 2

Figure I.34: Arc Frame 3

Figure I.35: Arc Frame 4

Figure I.36: Arc Frame 5

Figure I.37: Arc Frame 6

Figure I.38: Arc Frame 7

Figure I.39: Arc Frame 8

Figure I.40: Arc Frame 9

Figure I.41: Arc Frame 10

Figure I.42: Arc Frame 11

Figure I.43: Arc Frame 12

Figure I.44: Arc Frame 13

Figure I.45: Arc Frame 14

Figure I.46: Arc Frame 15

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Figure I.50: Arc Frame 19

Figure I.51: Arc Frame 20

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Figure I.61: Arc Frame 30

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Figure I.63: Arc Frame 32

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Figure I.82: Arc Frame 51

Figure I.83: Arc Frame 52

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Figure I.90: Arc Frame 59

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Figure I.94: Arc Frame 63

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Figure I.97: Arc Frame 66

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Figure I.99: Arc Frame 68

Figure I.100: Arc Frame 69

Figure I.101: Arc Frame 70

Figure I.102: Arc Frame 71

Figure I.103: Arc Frame 72

Figure I.104: Arc Frame 73

Figure I.105: Arc Frame 74

Figure I.106: Arc Frame 75

I.3 Test 5 - 175V - Arc 3

Figure I.107: Arc Frame 1

Figure I.108: Arc Frame 2

Figure I.109: Arc Frame 3

Figure I.110: Arc Frame 4

Figure I.111: Arc Frame 5

Figure I.112: Arc Frame 6

Figure I.113: Arc Frame 7

Figure I.114: Arc Frame 8

Figure I.115: Arc Frame 9

Figure I.116: Arc Frame 10

Figure I.117: Arc Frame 11

Figure I.118: Arc Frame 12

Figure I.119: Arc Frame 13

Figure I.120: Arc Frame 14

Figure I.121: Arc Frame 15

Figure I.122: Arc Frame 16

Figure I.123: Arc Frame 17

Figure I.124: Arc Frame 18

Figure I.125: Arc Frame 19

Figure I.126: Arc Frame 20

Figure I.127: Arc Frame 21

Figure I.128: Arc Frame 22

Figure I.129: Arc Frame 23

Figure I.130: Arc Frame 24

Figure I.131: Arc Frame 25

Figure I.132: Arc Frame 26

Figure I.133: Arc Frame 27

Figure I.134: Arc Frame 28

Figure I.135: Arc Frame 29

I.4 Test 5 - 175V - Arc 4

Figure I.136: Arc Frame 1

Figure I.137: Arc Frame 2

Figure I.138: Arc Frame 3

Figure I.139: Arc Frame 4

Figure I.140: Arc Frame 5

Figure I.141: Arc Frame 6

Figure I.142: Arc Frame 7

Figure I.143: Arc Frame 8

Figure I.144: Arc Frame 9

Figure I.145: Arc Frame 10

Figure I.146: Arc Frame 11

Figure I.147: Arc Frame 12

Figure I.148: Arc Frame 13

Figure I.149: Arc Frame 14

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Figure I.154: Arc Frame 19

Figure I.155: Arc Frame 20

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Figure I.162: Arc Frame 27

Figure I.163: Arc Frame 28

Figure I.164: Arc Frame 29

Figure I.165: Arc Frame 30

Figure I.166: Arc Frame 31

I.5 Test 6 - 200V - Arc 1

Figure I.167: Arc Frame 1

Figure I.168: Arc Frame 2

Figure I.169: Arc Frame 3

Figure I.170: Arc Frame 4

Figure I.171: Arc Frame 5

Figure I.172: Arc Frame 6

Figure I.173: Arc Frame 7

Figure I.174: Arc Frame 8

Figure I.175: Arc Frame 9

Figure I.176: Arc Frame 10

Figure I.177: Arc Frame 11

Figure I.178: Arc Frame 12

Figure I.179: Arc Frame 13

Figure I.180: Arc Frame 14

Figure I.181: Arc Frame 15

Figure I.182: Arc Frame 16

Figure I.183: Arc Frame 17

Figure I.184: Arc Frame 18

Figure I.185: Arc Frame 19

Figure I.186: Arc Frame 20

Figure I.187: Arc Frame 21

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Figure I.191: Arc Frame 25

Figure I.192: Arc Frame 26

Figure I.193: Arc Frame 27

Figure I.194: Arc Frame 28

Figure I.195: Arc Frame 29

Figure I.196: Arc Frame 30

Figure I.197: Arc Frame 31

I.6 Test 6 - 200V - Arc 2

Figure I.198: Arc Frame 1

Figure I.199: Arc Frame 2

Figure I.200: Arc Frame 3

Figure I.201: Arc Frame 4

Figure I.202: Arc Frame 5

Figure I.203: Arc Frame 6

Figure I.204: Arc Frame 7

Figure I.205: Arc Frame 8

Figure I.206: Arc Frame 9

Figure I.207: Arc Frame 10

Figure I.208: Arc Frame 11

Figure I.209: Arc Frame 12

Figure I.210: Arc Frame 13

Figure I.211: Arc Frame 14

Figure I.212: Arc Frame 15

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Figure I.214: Arc Frame 17

Figure I.215: Arc Frame 18

Figure I.216: Arc Frame 19

Figure I.217: Arc Frame 20

Figure I.218: Arc Frame 21

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Figure I.221: Arc Frame 24

Figure I.222: Arc Frame 25

Figure I.223: Arc Frame 26

Figure I.224: Arc Frame 27

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Figure I.226: Arc Frame 29

Figure I.227: Arc Frame 30

Figure I.228: Arc Frame 31

Figure I.229: Arc Frame 32

Figure I.230: Arc Frame 33

Figure I.231: Arc Frame 34

Figure I.232: Arc Frame 35

Figure I.233: Arc Frame 36

Figure I.234: Arc Frame 37

Figure I.235: Arc Frame 38

Figure I.236: Arc Frame 39

Figure I.237: Arc Frame 40

Figure I.238: Arc Frame 41

Figure I.239: Arc Frame 42

Figure I.240: Arc Frame 43

Figure I.241: Arc Frame 44

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Figure I.247: Arc Frame 50

Figure I.248: Arc Frame 51

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Figure I.250: Arc Frame 53

Figure I.251: Arc Frame 54

Figure I.252: Arc Frame 55

Figure I.253: Arc Frame 56

Figure I.254: Arc Frame 57

Figure I.255: Arc Frame 58

Figure I.256: Arc Frame 59

Figure I.257: Arc Frame 60

Figure I.258: Arc Frame 61

Figure I.259: Arc Frame 62

Figure I.260: Arc Frame 63

Figure I.261: Arc Frame 64

Figure I.262: Arc Frame 65

Figure I.263: Arc Frame 66

Figure I.264: Arc Frame 67

Figure I.265: Arc Frame 68

Figure I.266: Arc Frame 69

Figure I.267: Arc Frame 70

Figure I.268: Arc Frame 71

Figure I.269: Arc Frame 72

Figure I.270: Arc Frame 73

Figure I.271: Arc Frame 74

Figure I.272: Arc Frame 75

I.7 Test 6 - 200V - Arc 3

Figure I.273: Arc Frame 1

Figure I.274: Arc Frame 2

Figure I.275: Arc Frame 3

Figure I.276: Arc Frame 4

Figure I.277: Arc Frame 5

Figure I.278: Arc Frame 6

Figure I.279: Arc Frame 7

Figure I.280: Arc Frame 8

Figure I.281: Arc Frame 9

Figure I.282: Arc Frame 10

Figure I.283: Arc Frame 11

Figure I.284: Arc Frame 12

Figure I.285: Arc Frame 13

Figure I.286: Arc Frame 14

Figure I.287: Arc Frame 15

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Figure I.291: Arc Frame 19

Figure I.292: Arc Frame 20

Figure I.293: Arc Frame 21

Figure I.294: Arc Frame 22

Figure I.295: Arc Frame 23

Figure I.296: Arc Frame 24

Figure I.297: Arc Frame 25

Figure I.298: Arc Frame 26

Figure I.299: Arc Frame 27

Figure I.300: Arc Frame 28

Figure I.301: Arc Frame 29